

**TRENDS IN RESEARCH PRODUCTIVITY AND
COLLABORATION IN NIGERIA**

O.J. OGUNTOLA

APRIL 2025

**TRENDS IN RESEARCH PRODUCTIVITY AND
COLLABORATION IN NIGERIA**

By

OLADOTUN JUDE OGUNTOLA

[B.Tech. Project Management Technology (FUTA)]

Matric Number 232491

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements
for the Award of the Master of Information Science Degree of the
Department of Data and Information Science, University of Ibadan,
Nigeria

April 2025

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that Oladotun Jude Oguntola conducted this project at the Department of Data and Information Science, Faculty of Multidisciplinary Studies, University of Ibadan, under my supervision.

Oladotun Jude Oguntola

April 15, 2025

Date

Williams E. Nwagwu (PhD.)

April 15, 2025

Date

DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated to everyone who has started any course or endeavour and is struggling to finish it. Draw your inspiration from Jehovah – “The hands of Zerubbabel have laid the foundation of this house; his hands shall also finish it; and thou shalt know that the LORD of hosts hath sent me unto you” (The Holy Bible, Zechariah 4:9). Don’t stop! For only those who finish will get the reward. I am wishing you success.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I give all glory and honour to the Holy Trinity—God the Father, the Son, and the Holy Spirit—whose work in my life made it possible for me to undertake this endeavour. His grace enabled and sustained me through to the completion of this project.

I am especially grateful to my thesis supervisor, Dr. Williams Nwagwu, who was my soldier-teacher throughout this journey. Your patience, encouragement, and commitment pushed me beyond my limits. I am also deeply thankful for the connection you facilitated with Toluwase Asubiaro (Ph.D.), who provided invaluable guidance at the initial stages and helped me establish a strong footing in this project.

I extend my heartfelt gratitude to my parents, Mr. and Mrs. Peter Obisesan Oguntola and my siblings, whose unwavering support—financial, emotional, and spiritual—was critical to my successful completion of this work.

I recognise the National Open University of Nigeria (NOUN) for providing institutional access, which was indispensable in collecting data for this project—thank you for subscribing to Scopus. A special thanks to Adetayo Bamiduro, CEO of MAXDRIVE.ai, for approving my request to pursue further studies while continuing in my job role.

I also thank the entire D.D.I.S. staff, my lecturers, Prof. W.M. Olatokun, Dr. Funmilola.O. Omotayo, Dr. Adeola.O. Opesade, Dr. Janet.O. Adekanmbi, and Mrs. Folake.A. Longe, as well as all the non-teaching staff—you all were an important part of this journey.

Finally, to my friends, colleagues, and well-wishers who stood by me, followed up on my progress, and encouraged me—even during moments of delay—I am deeply grateful.

ABSTRACT

Research productivity is a critical driver of innovation and economic growth, yet concerns persist about Nigeria's output relative to global standards. Previous assessments have been inconsistent, often based on outdated or limited data. This study provides a systematic evaluation, analysing disciplinary trends, institutional performance, and co-authorship structures in Nigeria over a ten-year period (2014–2023).

A bibliometric approach was employed, utilising data from the Scopus database. Lotka's law was applied to examine author productivity, while co-authorship analysis categorises collaboration into local, regional, and international levels. Data preprocessing and statistical analyses were also conducted using Excel, Python, and bibliometric tools such as VOSviewer.

Results indicate an 11.54% increase in research output over the decade, with 122,891 publications recorded. However, growth stagnated after 2021. Federal universities lead in research output, benefiting from stronger funding and institutional support. Medical and Health Sciences dominate as the most productive discipline, followed by Natural and Social Sciences. Authorship distribution follows a highly skewed pattern, with 92.4% of authors publishing only once, reflecting weak continuity in scholarly engagement.

Nigeria has made notable progress, yet the concentration of research activity among a small subset of scholars suggests a systemic limitation in the country. Hence, to sustain growth, policies should prioritise targeted funding, institutional support mechanisms, and structured mentorship programs to encourage long-term research participation.

Keywords: Research Productivity, Bibliometrics, Nigeria, Collaboration, Academic Output

Word Count: 215

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Title Page	i
Certification	iii
Dedication	iv
Acknowledgements	v
Abstract	vi
Table of Contents	vii
List of Tables	xi
List of Figures	xii

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background to the Study	1
1.2. Statement of the Problem	14
1.3. Objectives of the Study	16
1.4. Research Questions	17
1.5. Justification of the Study	18
1.6. Scope of the Study	20
1.7. Definition of Terms	21

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Introduction	22
2.2. Research Production	23
2.3. Evaluation of Research production: reasons and relevance	24
2.4. Research Productivity	25
2.5. Indicators of research productivity.	26
2.6. Theories of Research Productivity	27
2.6.1. Lotka's Law	27
2.7. Global Outlook on Research Productivity	28
2.8. Disciplinary Divergence of Research Productivity	30
2.9. Institutional Factors Influencing Research Productivity	32
2.10. Benchmarking Research Productivity	35
2.11. Review of Empirical Literature on Research Productivity and Collaboration in Nigeria	37

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction	41
3.2. Context of the study	41
3.3. Research Design	42
3.4. Data Source	42
3.5. Data Collection	43
3.6. Organisation and Measurements of the Data	48
3.7. Data Cleaning	51

3.7.1. Country affiliation extraction	51
3.7.2. Country categorisation into Geographic Regions	51
3.7.3. Classification by Collaboration types	52
3.7.4. Institutional affiliation extraction	52
3.7.5. OECD Classification of Disciplines	53
3.8. Data Analysis	55
3.9. Ethical Considerations	57
3.10. Limitations	57

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Introduction	58
4.2. Analysis of Research Questions	58
4.2.1. Research Productivity Trends and Growth	58
4.2.2. Authorship Distribution from 2014 to 2023	66
4.2.3. Authorship Distribution (2014 to 2018)	67
4.2.4. Authorship Distribution (2019 to 2023)	68
4.2.5. International Collaborations	71
4.2.6. Collaborations Pattern and Author Productivity	73
4.2.7. Trends in Collaboration Levels	76
4.2.8. Collaboration Metrics	80
4.2.9. Publication trend across the OECD Disciplines	84
4.2.10. Collaboration types across the OECD disciplines	86
4.2.11. Institutional Features of the Top Ten institutions	88

4.2.12. Publication trends of Top Ten Nigerian Institutions	88
4.2.13. Collaboration trends of top ten Nigerian institutions	90
4.2.14. Disciplinary Productivity of top ten institutions	93
4.3. Discussions of Findings	96
CHAPTER FIVE: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS	
5.1. Introduction	101
5.2. Summary of the Findings	102
5.3. Conclusion	103
5.4. Recommendations	104
5.5. Suggestions for Further Studies	106
5.6. Limitations of the Study	107
References	108
Appendices	123
Appendix I: Full list of Collaborating countries with Nigeria	123
Appendix II: Full list of Collaborating countries with Nigeria	130
Appendix III: Yearly Authorship Distribution of Nigeria's Research Publications	143

LIST OF TABLES

Table 3.1: Dataset A. – Metadata of the Research production in Nigeria from 2014 – 2023.	49
Table 3.2: Dataset B – Countries/Territories involved in producing the publications in dataset A.....	50
Table 3.3: Dataset C -- Nigerian institution, their abbreviations and aliases.	50
Table 3.4: Final dataset variables.....	53
Table 4.1: Yearly Publications and Growth Rate	60
Table 4.2: Authorship Frequency Table	64
Table 4.3: Distribution across the collaborations type.....	69
Table 4.4: Top 20 most prolific individual and co-authors	74
Table 4.5: Collaboration Level per year	76
Table 4.6: Comparison of Collaboration Metrics	80
Table 4.8 Annual Productivity trend across disciplines.....	85
Table 4.9: Disciplinary Productivity across Collaboration Types	86
Table 4.10: Yearly research output of the top Nigerian institutions.....	88
Table 4.11 Institutional Productivity across OCED Disciplines	94

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 3.1: Basic Search Bar	45
Figure 3.2 Advanced query Bar	45
Figure 3.3 Export options	46
Figure 3.4 Export page.....	46
Figure 3.5 Scopus Intuitive filter interface	47
Figure 3.6 OECD Disciplinary Classification	54
Figure 4.1: Annual Publications trend	59
Figure 4.2: Year-Over-Year growth formula.....	60
Figure 4.3: Year-Over-Year (YOY) Growth (2014–2023).....	61
Figure 4.4: Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR).....	62
Figure 4.5: Overall Authorship distribution	66
Figure 4.6: Authorship distributions (2014 to 2018)	67
Figure 4.7: Authorship distributions (2019 to 2023)	68
Figure 4.8: Publication trend of the different Collaboration types	70
Figure 4.9: Top 20 Collaborating Countries with Nigeria	71
Figure 4.10: Network Map of Nigeria’s Collaborating Countries.....	72
Figure 4.11: Author Collaboration Network Map	73
Figure 4.12: Yearly Trend of the Collaborative Coefficient	82
Figure 4.13: Disciplinary distribution by OECD discipline	83

Figure 4.14: Publication Trend by OECD Disciplines	84
Figure 4.15: Productivity of Top Ten Nigerian Institutions	87
Figure 4.16: Publication Trend Analysis by Institutions	89
Figure 4.17: Collaboration types of Top Ten Institutions	90
Figure 4.18: Heat Map of Collaboration for the Top Ten institutions.....	91
Figure 4.19: Percentage of Collaboration for the Top Ten Institutions	92
Figure 4.20: Productivity of Top Ten Institutions across Discipline.....	93
Figure 4.21: Productivity Distribution of Top Ten Institutions by Discipline	95
Figure III.1 Authorship Distribution for 2014	151
Figure III.2 Authorship Distribution for 2015	152
Figure III.3: Authorship Distribution for 2016.....	153
Figure III.4: Authorship Distribution for 2017	154
Figure III.5: Authorship Distribution for 2018.....	155
Figure III.6: Authorship Distribution for 2019.....	156
Figure III.7: Authorship Distribution for 2020.....	157
Figure III.8: Authorship Distribution for 2021	158
Figure III.9: Authorship Distribution for 2022	159
Figure III.10: Authorship Distribution for 2023.....	160

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Traditionally, productivity measures performance by comparing the output of a product with the input or resources required to produce it. Input may include labor, equipment, or financial resources (Kenton, 2024). In a broader context, productivity is a versatile concept applied across various fields due to its ability to optimise the relationship between inputs—such as resources, time, and effort—and outputs, including results, goods, or services. Kenton further explains, "In the business world, productivity is a measure of the efficiency of a company's production process, calculated by measuring the number of units of a product produced relative to labor hours or by measuring net sales relative to labor hours" (Kenton, 2024 p.1).

In economics, productivity is closely tied to economic growth, as increased productivity allows for more goods and services to be produced with the same resources, thereby driving economic expansion (Mankiw & Taylor, 2020). In management, organisational productivity emphasises improving team outcomes through strategies such as workflow optimisation, effective resource allocation, and fostering employee well-being (Davis & Cable, 2014; Shangguan, DeVaro & Owan, 2021). Similarly, in psychology, productivity is associated with factors like motivation, time management, and cognitive processes, which influence individual and collective performance (Vohs & Baumeister, 2016).

Within academia, however, the concept of productivity changes; it refers to measurable outputs of research activities, including publications, grants, and patents. It focuses on the effectiveness of generating high-quality outputs, such as peer-reviewed publications, patents, and inventions, making it a key area of interest. (Nicolaidis, 2014) underscores the significance of research productivity in advancing knowledge and fostering innovation, both of which are critical for national development. He argues that enhancing research productivity not only deepens scientific understanding but also drives economic growth and informs policymaking to address societal challenges.

Furthermore, (Konstantin, Yana, & Oksana, 2016; Odeyemi, Odeyemi, Bamidele, & Adebisi, 2019) highlighted the vital role of research productivity in promoting innovation and discovery. Odeyemi et al (2019) further illustrated that research productivity serves as a valuable metric for managing limited resources, enabling funding bodies to prioritise support for highly productive individuals and institutions. This ensures the efficient allocation and utilisation of scarce research funds (Myeki & Temoso, 2019).

Research productivity is closely linked with research production which reflects the different dimensions of academic output. While research productivity focuses on the quality, impact, and frequency of scholarly contributions (Salisu & Salami, 2020; Nicolaidis, 2014), research production generally refers to the volume or quantity of output generated, including the number of articles published (Abramo & D'Angelo, 2014). The latter is often considered an indicator of academic engagement while research productivity extends the scope by considering the significance and effectiveness of the academic contributions, especially in terms of their impact on knowledge creation, policy, and societal development. Therefore, while research production captures the output itself, research productivity assesses the

relevance and broader implications of that output, making it a more objective measure of academic and innovation capabilities (Kifor, Teodorescu, Andrei, & Săvescu, 2021; Nicolaidis, 2014).

On the global stage, despite advancements in research output, a gap persists between developed and developing nations in respect of research production. Developed countries continue to dominate the global research landscape, while developing nations are increasingly striving to improve their contribution to global research. As (Ndibuza, 2021) and (Diop & Asongu, 2023) emphasised, despite the general increase in output from developing regions, Africa still faces challenges in catching up with the volume and quality of research produced by countries in regions like Europe and North America, the largest region, sub-Saharan, contributing less than 1% of the global research as of 2018 (Fonn et al., 2018).

Within Africa, South Africa, Egypt, Nigeria, and few other African countries leading in research production, have demonstrated notable growth (Wagdy, 2022). South Africa between a period of 17 years (2005 - 2021) recorded a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 7.62% growth through those years, indicating at least 7.62 % growth yearly (Research report, 2021). As for Egypt, the growth reported is up to 22% between 2020 and 2019 (Wachira, 2022). Interestingly, Nigeria, who produced almost 50% less than these countries in 2022, was reported to have experienced a 4.7% increase in research output over the last two decades, indicating the potential for continued growth (Wagdy, 2022).

Observing from history, the evolution of research in Nigeria is basically linked to the country's political, economic, and educational history. Logically, we can trace Nigeria's formal engagement with academic research to the colonial era (Ajayi, 1975), when the first tertiary institutions were established, since HEIs are the major source of research production.

Although the Higer College at Yaba was founded in 1934, the University of Ibadan, founded in 1948 as a college of the University of London, is commonly referred to as the pioneering academic research center in Nigeria. This is because establishing the Higher College was largely aimed at producing administrative personnel for the colonial government, rather than fostering research-driven innovations (Abrokwa, 2017). Consequently, research output was minimal, and academic publications from Nigerian scholars were sparse.

With Nigeria's independence in 1960, the focus of higher education began to shift towards nation-building and addressing local challenges. The Nigerian government invested in the expansion of universities, with the establishment of several other key institutions such as Ahmadu Bello University (1962), University of Lagos (1962), and Obafemi Awolowo University (1961) (Eribo, 1996). These institutions became centers for academic research across various disciplines, including agriculture, education, and social sciences. Research output during this period grew steadily, but it was still limited by the young nation's economic capacity (Salisu & Salami, 2020). Nonetheless, Nigerian scholars began publishing in regional and international journals, particularly in fields like tropical medicine, agriculture, and natural sciences, which were highly relevant to the country's development needs.

The 1980s marked a significant turning point in Nigeria's research output due to economic downturns, political instability, and the structural adjustment programs (SAPs) imposed by the International Monetary Fund (IMF). Funding for universities was severely cut, leading to a decline in both the quality of education and research infrastructure (Babalola et al, 1999). The impact of these cuts was felt across all fields, but especially in scientific research, where access to laboratory equipment, materials, and journals became increasingly difficult.

In addition to funding challenges, the period witnessed a massive brain drain, now recently termed in the country as “Japa” (Ogunode, NGEZACK, & Usi, 2024), with many Nigerian academics emigrating to Europe, North America, and other regions in search of better opportunities. As a result, the number of research publications originating from Nigerian institutions sharply declined during this period, as scholars faced limited opportunities for research collaboration, both locally and internationally.

As global connectivity increased with the advent of the internet and digital communication, Nigerian academics found new opportunities to collaborate with international scholars (Igwe, Achike, & Nwanguma, 2021). Government initiatives aimed at rejuvenating the educational sector, including the establishment of the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) in 2011, provided much-needed financial support for academic research. TETFund began allocating funds specifically for research and innovation, resulting in a modest but steady increase in publications (Echono, 2023).

During this period, there was also a notable rise in international collaborations, as Nigerian scholars increasingly partnered with foreign institutions, particularly in areas like health sciences, engineering, and the social sciences. The research output grew significantly, aided by the participation of Nigerian academics in diaspora networks that facilitated access to international funding and publishing platforms.

Nigeria, being the largest country on the African continent and country with the largest number of research institutions is unsurprisingly a major contributor to the rate of research growth in Africa. The major players in the Nigerian research production system are the Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), primarily, universities, then polytechnics, and other specialised research institutes. A steady growth in scientific productivity was reported for Nigeria between

1997 and 2007, in the field of biomedicine (Ajuwon, Auston, Raghavan, Kotzin, & Holfman, 2011). Also, Nigeria is the most productive in computer science research in the sub-Saharan region, only after South Africa (Harsh et al., 2021).

Regarding the direction of the trend, (Shkliarevsky, 2022), noted discord in the results of several studies. Though some reported a decline in research productivity over the last several decades, the authors observed that each study's conclusion was subject to the data source. For example, according to both Scopus, Web of Science (WoS) databases, and the Academia platform, the country has the most presence in all the three databases, contributing 54% of the entire computer science research in sub-Saharan (Harsh et al., 2021).

A common report in previous studies on the status, trends, and growth of research production in Nigeria has been the low productivity of Nigerian researchers (Afolabi, Popoola, Adoghe, Atayero, & Fayomi, 2019). Although this is not the case every time as some report high productivity. But this report of low productivity is usually not backed up by objective figures. Although the acclaimed discrimination of African science in the WoS database could be the logical explanation for the difference yet even based on data from the same Scopus database. (Galadanci, Muaz, Mukhtar, 2016) reported a significant difference in the total number of publications for these same institutions. Although it is a positive significant trend, this inconsistency in evaluation indicates a difference in the methodology and this may be consequential if it misleads the strategic leadership for which the information is meant to guide.

The story of how the intellectual experience of an institution has evolved can be depicted by analysing its research productivity trends (Atieno, Onyancha, & Kwanya, 2022)). The Nigeria university system comprises 274 universities, including 149 private-owned, 63 state government-owned and 63 Federal government-owned universities (Statista, 2024). As

of 2021, the Nigerian University commission (NUC), the regulatory organisation governing the activities of all universities in the country boasts of a stunning 77,000 researchers in the university system, which undisputably is the largest on the African continent.

Fortunately, most rankings and evaluations of universities are based on their number of publications, hence, institutions prioritise their faculty's productivity and even subject promotions and recognitions to productivity (Owan & Asuquo, 2022). Regrettably, research outputs from Nigerian universities are disproportionately lower when compared to other countries with fewer number of institutions in the same Africa (Ani & Bosire Onyanha, 2012), i.e., South Africa. Although, many attribute this unproportionate productivity to factors like limited funding, heavy workload from teaching, etc.

Nonetheless, several institutions have been found to stand out based on their past productivity performance. For instance, Afolabi et al., (2019), reported an increasing trend in the research productivity of some Nigerian institutions (i.e., University of Ibadan, University of Lagos, and Obafemi Awolowo university) between 2008 and 2010, based on data from the Scopus database. Although a contrary finding by (Ani & Bosire Onyanha, 2012), reported a decreasing trend for the same set of institutions within the same period, but based on data from the Web of science database. Yet a more recent evaluation by (Harsh et al., 2021) which explored multiple data sources confirms that the WoS database lists Covenant University (CU) as 3rd most productive institution in computer science research in sub-Sahara while University of Ibadan was ranked 1st, Obafemi Awolowo University (OAU), CU and University of Lagos (UNILAG) ranked 5th, 7th, 8th respectively, according to the Scopus database.

The clique of top universities comprising federal universities has been explained to be because of several factors including the funding support from the federal government. (Salisu & Salami, 2020 p. 29) hinted that Federal universities led the drive for research productivity in Nigeria due to "the numerous privileges they enjoyed from the federal government and others.". Most of the analysis of university publications utilised metrics like, Total outputs, Total no of First Authored Publications, Single Authored Publication, Total Citations, Average Publication per year (Salisu & Salami, 2020). Institutions with a wide scope of coverage regardless of their size and governance structure can produce high quality research. Productivity in one discipline of an institution can influence the productivity of others. The academic environment can influence individual research productivity (Bonaccorsi et al., 2021).

Besides institutional divergence, research productivity varies considerably across disciplines, a pattern seen both globally and within Nigeria. Durodolu, Adeleke, & Ojo, (2019) and Bornmann, (2016) show that fields like medicine, agricultural sciences, and engineering tend to have higher publication counts due to their immediate relevance to societal needs and national development. In Nigeria, these fields have traditionally received more attention and funding, making those leaders in research output. This is particularly evident in health and agricultural research, areas that align closely with Nigeria's focus on improving public health and food security (Okafor, 2010); Salisu & Salami, 2020).

In contrast, social sciences and humanities have historically been underfunded and, as a result, lag in research productivity. Ani & Onyancha, (2012) and Adetayo, Ojokuku, Babatunde, & Lawal, (2024) emphasised that these disciplines are often constrained by limited resources and fewer international collaborations. Additionally, because research in these areas

tends to focus on local or national issues, it may not attract the same level of global attention and funding as research in applied sciences.

The COVID-19 pandemic further underscored the impact of disciplinary differences on research productivity. During this period, medical sciences and certain environmental sciences experienced a surge in productivity as researchers focused on urgent health issues. In contrast, fields like computer science and engineering faced disruptions due to the postponement of conferences and delays in peer review processes (Haghani, Abassi, Zwack, Shahhoseini, & Haslam, 2022; Harsh et al., 2021). This variability in productivity highlights the need for a diversified research focus, allowing Nigeria to strengthen contributions across a range of disciplines. Investing in underfunded disciplines, particularly the social sciences and humanities, can lead to a more balanced research landscape (Bonaccorsi, Belingheri, & Secondi, 2021).

Despite the recent growth in Nigeria's research output, the country faces numerous challenges that hinder its potential. One of the most prominent issues is limited funding. Research funding in Nigeria remains low, with an estimated 0.2% of GDP allocated for research and development, far below the 1% recommended by United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation [UNESCO] for African countries (Egbetokun et al., 2022). This limitation constrains Nigerian researchers, as they struggle to secure grants necessary for high-quality projects, advanced equipment, and international collaborations (Uwizeye et al., 2021).

Another pressing issue is the brain drain phenomenon, where skilled researchers leave Nigeria to pursue better opportunities abroad. Studies like (Igiri et al., 2021) and (Afolabi et al., 2019) underscore how the exodus of talented academics impacts Nigerian universities,

depriving institutions of experienced faculty who could mentor upcoming researchers and contribute to institutional growth. This pattern further exacerbates the uneven distribution of research output across Nigerian institutions, as the loss of senior academics limits their capacity to produce a high volume of publications.

Infrastructure is another challenge in Nigerian research. Many universities lack access to modern facilities, including updated libraries, scientific databases, and laboratory equipment, which are essential for rigorous research, particularly in fields like medicine and engineering. This is noted by Galadanci et al., (2016), who highlight the adverse effects of inadequate research infrastructure on the quality of academic output. Additionally, the heavy teaching loads and administrative responsibilities faced by many Nigerian academics reduce the time available for research activities, further limiting productivity (Durodolu, Adeleke, Ojo, 2019; Salisu & Salami, 2020).

In contrast to these challenges, there are significant opportunities for growth. The Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund), established in 2011, has provided critical financial support to Nigerian researchers, contributing to a gradual increase in publications and collaborative projects. TET Fund's targeted grants for research and capacity-building have enabled institutions to develop their academic potential and broaden their scope of international partnerships (Adebayo & Ayeni, 2017).

Moreover, Nigeria's expanding population of young academics presents a valuable resource for the future. Studies like Atieno et al., (2022) highlight the promise of young scholars in driving the next wave of Nigerian research productivity. Additionally, as global research priorities shift toward emerging fields like artificial intelligence, renewable energy,

and sustainability, Nigerian researchers are well-positioned to contribute substantially to these areas, addressing both local and international challenges (Undie et al., 2024).

Furthermore, a notable characteristic of Nigeria's research has been the growing importance of collaboration. In Nigerian institutions, the pattern of research collaboration has been on an upward trajectory across these three levels. The increasing trend of collaboration is reflected in multi-author publications, commonly referred to as "co-authorship" (Yeo & Lewis Marie, 2019 p.112). For instance, Atieno et al., (2022) reports that about 70% of over 640 papers were co-authored within a three-year period, highlighting the importance of author collaboration as a significant factor in the growth of research publications.

Collaboration is a general practice across many industries, including healthcare, education, or technology. According to Adelowo, Ilevbare, & Orewole, (2022), in a cornerstone study, the concept of collaboration is not static, and its definition varies across different fields. This variability is especially pronounced in the research industry, where collaboration is widely practiced due to its numerous benefits, such as career progression for collaborators, comparative advantage, and enhanced research productivity.

Generally, collaboration has positives benefits. This is because of the possibility of leveraging each other's strengths. Studying the impact of collaboration on research productivity, Lee & Bozeman, (2005) observed that despite the common practice of collaboration in the field of science, the benefit of collaboration is more often assumed than proven or investigated. The authors highlighted the various elements of collaboration that can influence productivity which includes division of labor, complementary skill, time efficiency, access to equipment, new skills learned from collaborator, communicating of new information, new publishing opportunities etc.

Usually, collaboration is the key approach/mechanism for mentoring new researchers (i.e. Graduates and PhD researchers). Although collaboration can be a plus for others, it may not be an optimal usage of time and effort for others due to the caliber or cadre of their collaborator. i.e., Professor – graduate student collaboration. However, the correlation degree between productivity and collaboration varies substantially among different areas or fields of specialisation (Abramo, D'Angelo, & Di Costa, 2009).

Several studies proved collaboration as a key factor in driving research productivity across various fields. Collaboration positively influences research output by enhancing knowledge exchange, increasing access to resources, and fostering innovation (Giovanni et al., 2021). For countries with limited resources, like Nigeria, collaboration is argued to be a critical driver of improved research outcomes (Adelowo et al., 2022).

Collaborations are typically categorised at three levels Local, Regional, or International. In developing countries like Nigeria, international collaborations have been particularly beneficial, providing Nigerian researchers with access to advanced research tools, global funding opportunities, and publication in high-impact journals (Akindele & Adebowale, 2013). Such collaborations have become increasingly essential as noted by Uwizeye et al., (2021) point out, for institutions with limited resources that rely on external support to maintain high research productivity.

Notably, these international collaborations are predominantly with the UK and the US, accounting for more than 66% of Nigeria's co-authored publications. Despite this, Nigeria's international collaboration ratio lags countries like Saudi Arabia and Egypt, both of which have collaboration ratios above 80%. Yet international collaboration has been associated with higher

research productivity, especially in developing countries (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development [OECD], 2019).

Additionally, Nigeria has become a hub for regional collaboration within Africa (Fagbayibo, 2024) . Initiatives such as the African Academy of Sciences (AAS) and the Coalition for African Research and Innovation (CARI) have facilitated stronger partnerships between Nigerian institutions and other African universities, fostering regional networks that address shared challenges in health, education, and technology (Dosso, Cassi, & Mescheba, 2023).

However, despite the growing trend of international collaborations, regional collaborations within Africa remain relatively low. According to Harsh et al., (2021) only 12% of co-authored papers have at least one co-author from within the same region in Africa, in the field of computer science. In the same study, Harsh et al., (2021) analysed co-authorship at the country and institution level using the whole counting method. This method attributes a co-authored paper as a whole publication produced by the institution or country of each co-author.

Afolabi et al., (2019) highlights the tendency of Nigerian researchers to prioritise partnerships with scholars in developed countries over regional collaborations. This preference is often motivated by the visibility and impact associated with international partnerships, as well as the opportunities for funding and publication in globally recognised journals (Harsh et al., 2021). Although such collaborations help increase Nigeria's research output and global standing, they may limit the potential benefits of addressing issues specific to the African context. Regional collaborations, though less common, are equally important for tackling challenges unique to Africa, such as public health issues, agricultural productivity, and educational development (Salisu & Salami, 2020).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Scientific publications are steadily increasing globally, with developed nations maintaining a dominant position (Henrique, 2023; Marginson, 2021). While developing countries are increasingly participating in the global research landscape (Salisu & Salami, 2020), concerns persist regarding the direction of Nigeria's research productivity. Despite possessing a talented workforce and a growing research infrastructure, Nigeria may not be reaching its full potential (Egbetokun et al. 2020) and this may potentially be hindering its contribution to global knowledge and development.

Unfortunately, assessing Nigeria's research progress is challenging due to a lack of consensus among scholars on the direction of productivity. Research often presents contradictory findings, with some studies reporting stagnation, inequality in growth across disciplines and other related challenges (Oyewole et al., 2019; Igiri et al., 2021; Odeyemi et al., 2019) while another result indicates an increasing productivity (Diop & Asongu, 2023). This inconsistency stems partly from a reliance on limited and often outdated datasets.

Furthermore, research on productivity and collaboration in Nigeria are often constrained to specific perspectives. While studies have examined factors influencing research output at various levels i.e. individual, institutional, national (LADIPO et al., 2022), and assessed productivity among specific professionals, i.e. medical doctors, librarians (Adepeju & Awogbami, 2021; Ogunsola et al., 2020; Saka & Tijjani Abubakar, 2018), there is a significant gap in analyses at the institutional and disciplinary levels. Existing studies that have explored these aspects are now outdated (Salisu & Salami, 2020; Ani & Onyanacha, 2012).

To address these limitations, a comprehensive assessment of past productivity trends and their influencing factors is crucial. Analysing trends within specific disciplines will allow us to identify areas of strength and weakness in Nigeria's research focus, pinpoint areas of excellence, and recognise high-performing universities and research institutions. Measuring these trends is useful for predicting future performance and planning Atieno et al., (2022).

While some studies have compared research output across institutions (Galadanci et al., 2016) and examined productivity within specific subjects (Egbetokun et al., 2022), and a few have analysed productivity trends (Ajuwon et al., 2011; Durodolu et al., 2019), a full analysis of Nigeria's research productivity and collaboration outlook remain elusive. Previous studies have been limited in their disciplinary scope and time coverage. Therefore, a more detailed, in-depth, and updated study is necessary. Hence, this study incorporates an institutional, national, and discipline-based perspective, utilising data from bibliometric databases with wide national coverage, unlike traditional sources used in previous research.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

Main Objective

This study analysed research productivity and research collaboration in Nigeria over a ten-year period (2014 - 2023).

Specific Objectives

Building upon existing research, it addressed five key objectives.

1. To quantify the publications produced by researchers in Nigeria over a 10-year period (2014-2023) and identify any trends in research productivity.
2. To examine the authorship distribution of Nigeria's research outputs.
3. To analyse the patterns of collaboration in Nigeria's research outputs, focusing on the collaboration types and levels.
4. To examine the research productivity and collaboration of scholars in Nigeria across various academic disciplines based on the OECD's six broad discipline categorisation.
5. To identify high-performing (top 10) institutions, examine their institutional features and their disciplinary productivity performance.

1.4 Research Questions

The research questions were framed to elicit specific insights that addressed gaps identified in the literature:

1. What is the quantity of publications produced by researchers affiliated with Nigerian Institutions between 2014 and 2023 and what are the trends in research productivity?
2. What are the distributions of authorship in Nigeria's research outputs.
3. What are the patterns of collaboration in Nigeria's research outputs, focusing on the collaboration types and levels.
4. What are the predominant fields/disciplines of research (OECD discipline areas) among Nigerian authors, and how does publication trends vary across these fields?
5. Who are high-performing (top 10) institutions and what are their institutional features and productivity per discipline?

1.5 Justification of the Study

Building upon the existing research on research productivity in Nigeria, this present study contributed to a deeper understanding of research productivity in Nigeria by addressing the objectives outlined above. The comprehensive analysis examined research productivity across multiple dimensions (quantity, collaboration, disciplinary and institutional variations) which will provide a more inclusive understanding of the current landscape in Nigeria. Furthermore, using recent data from 2014-2023, the study offered insights into contemporary trends and developments in Nigerian research.

Also, the identification of high-performing institutions and their characteristics in the study can serve as a benchmark for other institutions to model. Likewise, the findings of this study informed policy decisions aimed at enhancing research productivity, fostering collaboration, and supporting high-performing institutions. The insights gained from this research contributed to a broader understanding of research dynamics in developing countries, potentially informing research policies and practices in other contexts.

Generally, investigating research productivity in Nigeria is beneficial for various stakeholders. Analysing research productivity in Nigeria can create a more robust research ecosystem. It can guide strategic decision-making, optimise resource allocation, and elevate Nigeria's contribution to global research. The insights gained from this study can also serve as a model for other developing nations seeking to enhance their research capabilities.

Specifically, policymakers and funding agencies can use this data to strategically allocate resources and prioritise research aligned with national goals. Institutions can benchmark performance, allocate resources internally, and attract talent through a strong research profile. Researchers themselves can use the findings to improve their careers by understanding how productivity is measured and identifying collaboration opportunities and align their research efforts with emerging trends.

Principally, this study fills a critical knowledge gap by providing a complete and up-to-date analysis of research productivity in Nigeria. The findings have the potential to inform evidence-based policies and strategies for promoting research excellence and innovation in the nation.

1.6 Scope of the Study

This study investigated and analysed research productivity in Nigeria. However, to ensure a focused and manageable research effort, the scope was defined based on the period of review and geographical location. The study focused on the past ten years of research productivity in Nigeria, from 2014 – 2023. This timeframe allowed for capturing recent trends and growth patterns while maintaining a manageable data collection and analysis process.

Specifically, the analysis examined research productivity trends, collaboration patterns, institutional performance and cross-disciplinary differences in Nigerian institutions who have published in any Scopus-indexed journal within the period of consideration. Hence, this study excludes any non-peer-reviewed publications and any publications lacking complete authorship information.

The study acknowledged limitations related to data availability, particularly regarding publications not indexed in the Scopus database which is important to consider while providing insights into the trends in research productivity and collaboration within Nigeria's academic landscape. Also, this study did not delve into the quality or impact of individual research outputs nor explore the specific content or findings of individual research projects except for those relevant to the research findings.

1.7 Definition of Terms

1. **Research Productivity:** The quantity of research output produced by a researcher or institution, typically measured by publication count.
2. **Publication Count:** The total number of research outputs published by a researcher or institution, including journal articles, books, conference proceedings, etc.
3. **Citation Count:** The number of times a particular research output (article, book, etc.) is cited by other researchers in their publications.
4. **Collaboration:** The act of working jointly with others, particularly in research contexts, which can include co-authorship of publications or participation in joint research projects.
5. **Institutional Affiliation:** The organisation (e.g., university, research institute, private sector) with which a researcher is associated, which may influence their access to resources and support for research activities.
6. **Discipline-Specific Research:** Research activities categorised according to academic disciplines (e.g., natural sciences, social sciences) that may exhibit varying levels of productivity and collaboration.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

The essence of the literature review is to build a foundation for the study and to demonstrate how it advances knowledge leveraging on the existing works. Consequently, this chapter first conceptualises research production and research productivity. Then it examined the purpose of research evaluation, indicators and theories in research productivity, and the global outlook on research productivity. Finally, it progressively delved into a review of empirical studies on research productivity in Nigeria. The primary objective was to gather empirical evidence, theoretical frameworks, and methodological approaches to guide the current study.

2.2 Research Production

Research is defined as work conducted systematically to primarily increase a body of knowledge and aimed at uncovering new facts to gain knowledge needed for addressing problems and it involves how new knowledge can be applied to solve existing problems (Kabir, 2016, Chapter 1, p. 2). Production on the other hand, is described as the transformation process that generates specific outputs elements from a set of input elements (Frisch, 1965). In the field of knowledge production, primarily, the main human capital stock of inputs for both the teaching and research dimensions consists of the academic body (Verzillo & Santoni, 2011). Bringing the definition of the two keywords together, we can relate research production to the process of transforming human and financial resources into inputs to generate scientific outputs (i.e. an article) (Zhang, Bao, & Sun, 2016).

In essence, research production is equivalent to producing scientific knowledge which is pivotal to economic development. In 1st world countries like the USA and Germany, economic indicators of development such as GDP have been found to consistently correlate positively with their level research activities (Paprotny, 2021). Some studies have associated the increased level of research with national growth (Okokpujie, Fayomi, & Leramo, 2018). This is one reason why many developed countries invest billions of dollars research every year and some middle-income and developing countries like China and India are increasing the percentage of their national expenditures spent on doing research yearly (UNESCO, 2016; Zhang et al., 2016).

2.3 *Evaluation of Research production: reasons and relevance*

Measuring scientific or research production is a common practice done for various reasons. Some of these reasons are related to the general rationale for evaluating any production process which includes ensuring efficient use of the production inputs (material and human resources) for optimal production, providing empirical evidence and justification for investing further in the research (UK Healthy Universities Network, n.d.). The same report which focuses on “Why evaluate Research” further explicates that measuring of scientific production serves as a feedback mechanism, that is, the results of scientific production analysis assist policymakers and strategic decision makers to understand the trends in science and allocate resources appropriately. The implication of this measurement is that inequalities are unveiled in the production system, for example, gender disparity and disciplinary difference in research production. (UK Healthy Universities Network, n.d.). This growing practice according to Vitanov, (2016) is associated with reasons like limited funds allocation, requirements for transparency and accountability in research expenditure.

Measuring research production takes two broad dimensions as we see in past works, the qualitative and the quantitative approach. The quantitative approach depends uses certain bibliometric indicators, i.e. number of publications, to determine the output of a researcher while the qualitative approach depends on opinion of those in the academia, popularly referred to as, “Expert reviews” (Osegueda, 2003). Although most evaluations of research production are guided by the quantitative approach due to the ease of use for assessment (Verzillo & Santoni, 2011).

The quantitative approach also has its root found in two different models or techniques, mathematical and econometric. This categorisation is based on how the productivity measure is calculated. Whereas the mathematical model is the common bibliometric indicators based on the citation count, the h-index, or its variants (Abramo & D'Angelo, 2016), the econometric technique uses models like the Stochastic Frontier analysis, which uses regression analysis to estimate a production function (Zhang et al., 2016). An interesting observation is that the background or discipline of evaluators may have influenced the approach to research productivity.

2.4 *Research Productivity*

Research productivity is a multidisciplinary concept that is discussed, examined, and investigated in almost all domains or disciplines of study such as Accounting, Economics, Education, Information science, etc. to, (Daigle & Arnold, 2000; Maringe & Ojo, 2017; Hu & Li, 2020; Uwizeye et al., 2021). Its multifaceted nature makes it a concept of interest, studied across various institutions of education and research institutes (Dundar & Lewis, 1998; Garcia-Cano et al., 2019; Yusuf A.K., 2012).

The concept of Research productivity dates back as far as in the 1900s, when a Polish American scientist, Alfred Lotka, presented his findings about a study of publication by a group of physics and chemistry authors. One of his main findings was that, only few among this group of scholars produced more than 60% of the entire publication (Nicholls, 1986). Based on his work the set of scholars who produced more publications were deemed to be more scientifically productive than the others. Also, another scientist, Samuel Bradford in 1948, studied core scientific journals and discovered that it was dominated by only a few productive articles.

Subsequently, their approach became the most adopted definition of “Research Productivity”; “The number of publications per researcher”. Afterwards, several studies have defined Research Productivity as the quantity of publications per researcher to differentiate it from research visibility or impact 201(Abramo & D’Angelo, 2014) while others have used it as the general term used to describe both the quantity and the quality of the researchers’ publication (Agarwal et al., 2016).

2.5 *Indicators of research productivity.*

The productivity of a researcher can be measured using various indices. There are basic indices like the researcher’s total number of publications and total citation count. Yet, some argued that the productivity of researchers should not be determined based on mere figures and that these quantitative indicators should be used to guide the expert reviews (Working Group on Bibliometrics, 2016).

Also, there are other indices that are simple yet more thorough than the basic ones like the H-index and the i-10 index (Costas & Bordons, 2007) and more complex indices that adopt mathematical and statistical principles although derived from the h-(Abramo & D’Angelo, 2016). On the use of these metrics there is a call to see other approaches to research evaluation. Quoting (Shkliarevsky, 2022), "The indicators of research productivity we currently use is not reliable”, hinting that we need a new set of indicators.

2.6 *Theories of Research Productivity*

Theories provide a foundational framework for understanding research. They offer explanations, predictions, and insights into the factors influencing scholarly output. Several prominent theories have emerged in this field, each offering unique perspectives on the dynamics of research productivity. Specifically, the theories reviewed here include observations, postulations, and experiments conducted on research production data and were found to hold true most of the time. Some of the related theories on research productivity found in literature include Lotka's law, Price's theory, Mathew's theory, Bradford's law of scattering, Job satisfaction theory etc. However, this study reviewed only Lotka's law due to its relevance to the study.

2.6.1 Lotka's Law

Lotka's law, popularly referred to as the "inverse square law" was proposed in by an American scientist, Alfred Lotka in 1929. The scientist proposed the law after observing a pattern in the productivity frequency distribution of certain authors in the field of physics and chemistry and the number of their research outputs (Coile, 1978). His law states that "the number of persons making n contributions is about $1/n^2$ of those making one and the proportion of all contributors that make a single contribution is about 60%", "contributions" here refer to research publications (Coile, 1978, p. i). He translated his law into a formular that represents the relationship between authors and their research outputs. The relationship thus found to exist between the frequency y of persons making x contributions is $x^n y = \text{const}$ ", where n is approximately equal to 2. This law has since been a foundational theory for many other works that sought to measure scientific productivity, despite limitations and critics.

One of the limitations of Lotka's law was that it ignored the contributions of co-authors as it focuses on first authors only (Nicholls, 1986). The author himself acknowledged this limitation stating in his foot note, "Joint contributions have in all cases been credited to the senior author only" (Lotka, 1926 p.323). Also, (Coile, 1978) critiqued in his compilation of works which applied Lotka's law to authors in areas like humanities and map librarianship, to examine the possibility of its applicability. He mentioned that many of these works may have misinterpreted Lotka's law and that their conclusion on its applicability to other fields may be erroneous. Nevertheless, this law remains one of the theoretical bases that guide research works in scientific productivity.

2.7 *Global Outlook on Research Productivity*

No doubt, research production has increased globally across all continents, the quantity of research publications year on year reached 2.9 million articles in 2020, with 70% of this number being produced by few countries from Europe, America and Asia. Between 2010 and 2020, the compound growth rate of the world hit an all-time 4% (National Science Foundation (NSF), 2023), growth rate being the "percentage difference in the number of publications over a period of one year" (Nwagwu & Williams, 2022, p. 5). But the growth was interrupted by the global pandemic COVID 19 (Haghani et al., 2022), yet this unpredicted interruption did not affect all the continents. While most of the continents increased in the quantity of their yearly research outputs, some decreased in research growth when compared to their past performance.

Africa for instance, though low in research production when compared with other continents, is now leading the globe when it comes to research growth. According to (Diop & Asongu, 2023), "*Africa represents the highest rate of increase in research production*",

recording a 2.88% growth in its contribution to global knowledge from 1.25, between the years 2000 and 2019. This is the same period when Western Europe and North America recorded a significant decrease in their contribution to global knowledge, from 31.09% to 19.61% and from 35.245 to 25.63%, respectively. This indicates that Africa may be catching up gradually while Europe seems to be approaching a point of marginally diminishing returns while maintaining the lead in research production.

From the national perspective, obviously, most of the world leaders i.e. USA, UK, France, and Germany remain at the top position based on their quantity of research outputs while none of the African countries appeared in the top 50, according to SCImago data. But considering research growth, countries like Russia, India, China, and Brazil lead the group, increasing their research outputs by an average of 5% to 10% between 2010 to 2020 while the entire Africa increased by 1.4% (NSF, 2023), of which South Africa, Egypt and Nigeria are chief of the top 10 African countries contributing 92% of the entire African outputs respectively after two decades (Ali & Elbadawy, 2021).

Zeroing on Nigeria, the nation has notably grown its research output by about 4.7% in the last two decades (Wagdy, 2022), yet this number is quite insignificant when viewed on the globe landscape and when examined alongside its research workforce. However, contrasting Nigeria with the league of countries leading the global research growth, only India and Brazil appear to be in her peer group in terms of economy. India, like Nigeria, is classified as lower-middle-income country by the World Bank, while Brazil, although classified an upper-middle-income, has been trapped in that status for more than five decades (Otaviano Canuto, 2014). Yet both India and Brazil are making outstanding and significant contributions to global science, being in the top 13 of the world's research producers (NSF, 2023). This position them

as suitable benchmarks or model for countries like Nigeria if they seek to grow their research capabilities.

2.8 *Disciplinary Divergence of Research Productivity*

Bonaccorsi et al. (2021) in their study examined research productivity across five STEM disciplines, emphasising the importance of considering disciplinary differences when analysing research output. Ignoring these differences can lead to inaccurate conclusions, making assessments that overlook them questionable. Notably, differences in research productivity across disciplines often revolve around metrics such as the total number of citations received, citations per year, and the average number of co-authors.

Observable differences are particularly pronounced between pure sciences (e.g., Mathematics, Physics) and applied sciences (e.g., Engineering, Medicine, Computer Science). Over the past five years, Environmental Sciences and Engineering have emerged as the fastest-growing research fields. Some Medical Science disciplines have also shown significant growth, while fields in the Arts & Humanities and Social Sciences have experienced fluctuating trends. This indicates a shift in research focus, with STEM disciplines leading in research productivity. (Bonaccorsi et al., 2021)

Furthermore, the COVID-19 pandemic had a varied impact across different research disciplines. The Medical Sciences and some other natural science disciplines seemed to benefit the most during this period, likely due to increased focus on health-related research. Conversely, the Arts & Humanities and Social Sciences were significantly affected, with declines also noted in Computer Science and other Engineering disciplines. The decline in these fields may be attributed to canceled conferences, which particularly impacted on the Computer Science field, and a slower peer review process that likely affected Social Sciences

and the Arts & Humanities. The cause of the decline in productivity in certain disciplines may become clearer upon analysing 2021 publications. It remains to be seen whether the research was never conducted due to the pandemic or whether publications were simply delayed and later published in 2021 (Haghani et al., 2022).

Many factors can be responsible for the difference in research productivity across disciplines like disciplinary attributes. For instance, research productivity in pure science is naturally lower than in applied science due to the difference in the likelihood of citation and collaboration practice. Van Raan (2014) found that Engineering and Medicine papers typically have higher citation counts than Mathematics and Physics papers. This is partly because applied research often addresses current, high-impact issues that many other researchers reference in their work. Similarly, applied sciences often involve interdisciplinary research, bringing together experts from various fields to work on a common problem. This naturally leads to more co-authors and higher citation rates.

Other factors contributing to differences in productivity across disciplines include shifts in global research focus, administrative processes like the publication process, and unpredictable events such as the COVID-19 pandemic. For instance, the emerging focus on climate change led to a significant increase in research output in Environmental Sciences between 2000 and 2015, as the issue garnered substantial global attention and funding (Bornmann et al., 2016). More recently, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) have captured global interest, becoming integral to research across various fields due to their transformative potential (Undie et al., 2024).

2.9 *Institutional Factors Influencing Research Productivity*

Whether research productivity is high or low, knowing the factors that inhibit or facilitate is important for various reasons. First is that it informs policy makers on possible intervention and support programs that can be done to assist the individual researcher to boost productivity and hereby increase institutional and national productivity. Second, at the institutional level, the knowledge of these factors guides hiring committees to identify certain traits and characteristics of highly productive researchers and then build the requirements into the recruitment process. Furthermore, a clear understanding of these factors provides an empirical basis for efficient funds allocation.

Apart from the individual-related factors, the factors reported in literature, found to contribute to researchers' productivity include availability of funds, institutional research policies, leadership or ownership structures, training and resources, workload and so on (Heng et al., 2020; LADIPO et al., 2022). All these classified as institutional factors clearly due to their macro effects which are outside the control of the individual researcher. Interestingly, this category of factors has been reported to have a greater influence on research productivity than even the individual factors.

Largely, funding is a common factor identified to affect research productivity. For instance, Konstantin et al., (2016) assessed the effect of funding and other factors including demographics characteristics on the research productivity of about 2,633 academics and reported that funding has a greater impact on research productivity than age or any other demographic characteristics. But despite its high importance, researcher in Nigeria seem to be disadvantaged as the common report is that availability of funding is extremely low.

Uwizeye et al., (2021) presented the opinion of 28 studies on research productivity in Africa, of which the majority were on Nigerian, the common factor was availability of funding. Furthermore, Egbetokun et al., (2022) provided a more objective insight to the subject of funding as a factor of research productivity in Nigeria. Using both qualitative and quantitatively approaches the authors, referring the only publicly available data on research funding, revealed that Nigeria's allocation for research was only 0.2% of her GDP as against the 1% recommended by UNESCO for African counties. Their qualitative data uncovered, insights from a TETFUND official admitting that the current funding for research is not enough to push the economy forward.

In addition to funding, the authors stressed the key position of institutional support for researchers. *“The capacity of a research institution to provide effective logistical support for research professionals will directly affect its overall output and quality”* (Egbetokun et al., 2022, p. 7). Institutional support is a component in the research system that can facilitate the research production process. They may include administrative functions like research proposal writing, or training on financial management, and so on. However, most researchers in Nigerian express dissatisfaction due to this institutional support.

Aside from institutional support, some other institutional factors found to influence research productivity related to its observable characteristics. They include location, ownership or management type, size, age (Lee, 2021). Regarding institutions' location, institutions situated in metropolitan areas tend to attract better talents than those in the suburbs and as such tend to be more productive. The influence of an institution's ownership of management structure largely influences its research productivity since it determines its funding structure.

Globally, government owned institutions are generally known to have more access to funding and as such are more productive than their counterparts owned by private organisations. Similarly in Nigerian, Government owned institutions are general found to be more productive than private owned institutions, particularly those owned by the federal government (i.e. University of Nigeria, University of Ibadan), yet the narrative is changing as few private-owned institution (i.e. covenant) are emerging to challenge those backed by the federal government.

Equally, comparing institutions' research productivity without considering their sizes may seem unfair. Since, it is plausible that institutions with larger staff capacity and graduate output, especially at the post-graduate level, would have higher research productivity. Yet that may not always be the case as Bonaccorsi et al., (2021) reports that the relationship between institutions' size and research productivity is not specific and may be dependent more on the discipline. Also, institutional age is another factor found in literature to correlate positively with research productivity. Although, like size it may seem unfair to compare older generation institutions with the younger ones, age is one interesting factor that positively influences productivity. In the Nigerian context, 1st generation institutions still dominate that top position in Research productivity (Ani & Onyancha, 2012).

Lastly, time dedicated to research is another factor found to influence the productivity of researchers. This is usually difficult to measure objectively but a common assumption in previous studies is that time available for research is associated with on the researchers' workload (LADIPO et al., 2022). Hence, some have determined the time available for research based on respondents' estimate of time dedicated to research, some others estimated this using the size of the faculty, the size of the university, and the graduate to faculty ratio. Considering

time available for researcher in Nigerian institutions, many studies have reported low time available due to workload and distraction from other activities, i.e. teaching, administration etc. (Egbetokun et al., 2022). Each of these works addressed different areas of research productivity, like policies, factors and determinants, and measures of research productivity (Costas & Bordons, 2007).

2.10 *Benchmarking Research Productivity*

Benchmarking research productivity involves comparing an individual, department or an institution's research performance against external standards or peers. It is common practice in various fields, including education, business, and healthcare. In academia, benchmarking can be used to identify areas for improvement, set performance goals, allocate resources more effectively, and promote accountability.

An OECD report on benchmarking reveals that “The benchmarking exercise provided an opportunity to review the current state of higher education” in countries and helped to “identify some pressing performance issues facing higher education systems”. Also combining indicators at the national level poses a complexity in “making summary judgements about the performance of higher education systems” (OECD, 2019, Chapter 8). According to the same report, several benefits can be derived from benchmarking research performance, which includes timely update of the knowledge base on all aspects of higher education which provides policy makers with ready information or decision making. Another advantage is that it helps to identify important gaps in data and evidence. Then a benchmarking exercise involves data development or curation which can lead to the “creation of a benchmarking data infrastructure that can be automatically refreshed as new data becomes available” (OECD, 2019, Chapter 8).

Benchmarking is not a simple process. Harzing, (2016) highlights Five (5) tough decisions to be made during benchmarking. Firstly, “What to benchmark”. This refers to the basis of the benchmark, in this case may be, publications, citations, research fundings, social impact, etc. Next is to “choose a suitable indicator”. Indicators may be publication counts, citation counts, h-index, Journal Impact factors (JIF), etc. Then, “selecting a relevant data source” is key. Many sources are available including traditional bibliometric sources like Scopus and WoS, or other databases like Google Scholar, Open Alex, etc. to ensure inclusiveness for disciplines or countries that may not be well represented in the traditional databases.

Fourthly, it is also important to “determine the level to be benchmarked”, whether it is at the individual level, departmental level, faculty level, etc., although benchmark level will largely depend on the purpose of benchmarking. For instance, individual level benchmarking, though insightful, may provide too many unnecessary details if the purpose is to identify areas of excellence and improvement points in an institution. Finally, a “benchmarking standard” should be determined. For example, in making this decision for institutional benchmarking, Harzing, (2016) suggested that institutions within the same mission group may be chosen as a standard or an international institution, especially one who has increased their performance substantially and faced similar conditions or challenges.

Benchmarking has been adopted in many educational institutions to establish performance and or gaps, find better ways of doing things, and seek continuous improvement in areas like university administration (Pulatkhon, 2007). It has also been conducted to “improve their international reputation and ranking in terms of research outputs, research grants, and publications”. (Lopez, 2019)

2.11 Review of Empirical Literature on Research Productivity and Collaboration in Nigeria

Nwagwu, (2016) examined biomedical research publications in West Africa between 2005 and 2014. The study identified Nigeria, Ghana, Senegal, and Mali as top producers of biomedical research, with the West African Journal of Medicine being a key publication outlet. Using bibliometric methods, the study analysed journal impact and research productivity, revealing that Nigeria, Ghana, and Senegal contributed significantly to the biomedical literature. The findings underscored the need for more collaborative research in the region.

Wusu & Lazarus, (2018) studied trends in Library and Information Science (LIS) research from 1980 to 2017. This bibliometric study analysed 500 of the most cited articles, exploring the impact of factors such as the number of authors, institutional affiliation, and document types on citation frequency. The study identified key trends in LIS research, including significant contributions from the USA, England, China, South Africa, and Nigeria. The authors noted a growing interest in topics like information literacy and open access, which are expected to dominate future LIS research.

Mantikayan & Abdulgani, (2018), reviewed several journal publications with the aim of uncovering the reasons for disparity in scientific production among scholars by examining the possible factors research production. The author's conclusion was that the findings of these publications are often conflicting depending upon the research methodology and the academic discipline in consideration. Interestingly, the contradiction in the findings observed with the demographic data can be explained by the differences in the academic discipline since disciplines differ and so also the requirements.

Durodolu et al., (2019) studied trends and patterns of medical research in Nigerian universities over ten years: A bibliometric analysis. This study investigates the trends and patterns of medical research in Nigerian universities over ten years. Analysing Scopus-indexed publications, the authors find a steady increase in research output, with the Nigerian Journal of Clinical Practice being the most widely used journal. The study highlights the growing trend of international collaboration, particularly with researchers from the United States, and suggests that research visibility has improved over the years, with a 9.5% growth rate in medical research productivity.

Shonhe, (2020) conducted a bibliometric analysis of research on continuous professional development (CPD) for librarians. The study analysed 77 records from the Web of Science using R and VOSviewer. The results revealed that the USA, UK, and Australia led CPD research, while Nigeria and South Africa were prominent in Africa. The author called for further research in public and school libraries to address CPD gaps in African countries.

Anwar & Tang, (2021) analysed publishing trends in Library Philosophy and Practice during the COVID-19 pandemic. Their findings revealed that India and Nigeria were the most productive countries, with collaborative publishing on the rise. The study observed a significant publishing surge in 2020, followed by a decline in 2021. Similarly, the same authors compared the research productivity of Nigerian and Indian authors in Library Philosophy and Practice between 2008 and 2013. The study found that Nigerian authors had more publications than Indian authors, with 2010 marking the peak. The authors also examined citation patterns and identified the most productive authors from both countries (Anwar & Tang, 2020).

Gireesh, Kunwar, Abhishek, & Somesh, 2020 conducted a Scientometrics analysis of research output in the Library Philosophy and Practice e-journal from 1998 to 2019. The study found that 2019 saw the highest number of published articles, with growth in research productivity. Collaboration, citation patterns, and country-wise publication distribution were also examined.

Okon, Owan, & Owan, (2022)) examined the contribution of mentorship practices to research productivity among early-career academics in educational psychology in South-South Nigeria. The study surveyed 723 early-career researchers from 19 universities using a quantitative ex-post facto design. Findings indicated that cloning and apprenticeship mentorship approaches significantly contributed to research productivity, while nurturing had a minimal impact. The authors suggested strengthening mentorship practices to enhance research productivity among early-career researchers.

Adetomiwa, Akintola, Ejiwoye, & Olabisi (2023) assessed the level of academic staff research productivity in private universities in Southwestern Nigeria. Using a correlational survey design, they selected 657 academic staff across various ranks through proportional and stratified random sampling techniques. The study found that research productivity was low, with a mean score of 2.02, below the normative benchmark of 3.00. The authors recommended increased investment in research and the integration of emerging digital trends to improve productivity.

A report by the Elsevier's senior vice president, Carlos Henrique elicited the yearly research growth and overall growth rate of the G-20 countries for a 21-year period (1999 – 2022). His finding reveals that Indonesia led the group with a 21% yearly growth followed by Saudi Arabia, China and India, all recording a 16%, 14.7% and 11.2% yearly growth

respectively. South Africa, being the only African country recorded a 7.8%. However, on the growth rate side, India and China recorded a consistent 9.3% and 9.7% within that period (Henrique, 2023).

Folayan et al. (2023) explored gender differences in research productivity and collaboration in dentistry in Nigeria. The study revealed that female researchers had higher productivity and citation counts, with more females listed as first authors. The authors called for further investigation into cultural gender influences on these outcomes.

Khali, Babalola, & Unegbu, (2024) investigated the impact of research skills on research productivity among librarians in Nigerian public universities. Despite high research skill levels, the study found no significant correlation with actual productivity, suggesting that institutional support and incentives might play a more significant role in boosting productivity. Adetomiwa and Igiri et al. (2021) focused on challenges faced by Nigerian academics, particularly research funding constraints, which hinder productivity. The study emphasised the need for a Special Research Trust Fund to support research development across the country.

Similarly, Adetayo et al., (2024), evaluated the impact of mentoring on research productivity among librarians in southwestern Nigerian universities. The study found that mentoring positively influenced research productivity, particularly career support, and advocated for structured career mentoring to enhance research output.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter outlines the methodology employed for eliciting the publication trends, analysing the collaboration impact both within and outside Nigeria while comparing the productivity across various Nigerian institutions, and examining productivity across different academic disciplines. It provided a framework for how data were collected, processed, and analysed to achieve the stated research objectives, including a brief overview of the Nigerian research space which provides a context into the population, as well as a detailed design of the study. The methodology was structured to ensure that the research was conducted with rigor, accuracy, and ethical consideration. It directly addressed all the research objectives outlined in chapter one, ensuring that the data collected effectively supported the analysis of collaboration and productivity trends among scholars in Nigeria.

3.2 Context of the study

This study focused on the Nigerian research ecosystem which comprises over 270 higher education institutions (HEIs), including universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education (National Universities Commission (NUC), 2024), and over 30 research institutes and centers (Commonwealth Network, 2025). The research population for this study therefore comprised all research publications (i.e., articles, books, conference papers, patents, etc.) affiliated with researchers from these Nigerian institutions and published between 2014 and 2023. This time frame enables us to capture the recent trends in research productivity and collaboration, thereby providing a contemporary overview of scholarly output in Nigeria.

3.3 Research Design

This study employed a bibliometric research design, a quantitative approach that systematically analyses publication and citation data to evaluate research productivity, trends, and collaboration. Bibliometric methods offer an objective and replicable means of measuring scholarly output, making them particularly suitable for assessing academic contributions over time (Moed, 2005). The choice of bibliometric analysis is based on its ability to provide a quantifiable assessment of research output. Unlike subjective evaluations, bibliometric methods rely on measurable indicators such as publication count and authorship trends to offer clear insights into research productivity. This ensures that the evaluation remains unbiased, and data driven. Additionally, bibliometric methods are highly reproducible and scalable, allowing application across different datasets and extension to future studies, making them adaptable to various research contexts (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017).

3.4 Data Source

Three primary sources were consulted to retrieve the datasets used for carrying out this study, the Scopus database, the NUC website, and the Commonwealth Network website. Scopus, an Elsevier product, is recognised as the largest abstract and citation databases globally, encompassing over 19,000 titles from more than 5,000 international publishers. The use of standardised databases such as Scopus ensures data reliability and comparability, further strengthening the credibility of the bibliometric assessments. It is a trusted, source-neutral, comprehensive, academic database of abstract and citations for research literature. Also, it covers a wide range of subjects including medicine, science, technology, social science, and arts and humanities (Scopus.com). Scopus was preferred over other alternatives like Web of Science (WoS) because it indexes a slightly higher number of African journals than the WoS.

On the other hand, the NUC being the government institution responsible for “granting approval for the establishment of all higher educational institutions” according to the Council for Higher Education Accreditation (CHEA), provides a list of all accredited institutions in the country on their website, making the data accessible. This source was greatly preferred to other sources like Wikipedia because of the completeness of the dataset. Likewise, the Commonwealth Network provides a list of all research institutions in Nigeria. These sources were carefully selected from the pool of options available considering their integrity, and their authority in the domain of the respective data objects.

3.5 Data Collection

Three different datasets were wrangled to form the data used for assessing the research objectives. Dataset A is the main bibliometric data on research publications, contains objects like title, author, language, citation metrics, institutional and other bibliographical information. Dataset B contains the lists of countries/territories involved in producing the research publications contained in dataset A. Dataset C comprised the list of all accredited Nigerian universities and Commonwealth recognised institutions alongside their institutional features was collected from the NUC and the Commonwealth Network websites separately.

Dataset A was accessed at <https://www.scopus.com> on the 22nd of October 2024 (requires institutional access to Scopus), via the Scopus search interface by inputting in basic search bar (figure 3.1), the keyword ‘nigeria’ in the “*Search documents*” section and selecting “*affiliation*” in the “*Search within*” section. Also, the year range was set to 2014 – 2023 to filter only for the desired period. This returned the record of all documents that matched the keyword within that period based on the document’s affiliation. However, toggling the Scopus “*Advance query*” search bar (figure 3.2) reveals a single query whose results is equivalent to search

procedure applied above, although using this query ensured consistency. **“(AFFIL (nigeria) AND PUBYEAR > 2012 AND PUBYEAR < 2024)”**

Afterwards, the data was downloaded in segments according to the Scopus subject areas. This ensured scalability and helped to overcome the 20,000 rows limitation set by Scopus for single CSV exports (see figure 3.3.& 3.4). Fortunately, the segmented download is consistent with the original methodology as it allowed for the easy labelling of the dataset by the subject areas since they are not contained in the dataset itself. The individual CSV files (29) for each of the 28 subject areas represented were merged into a single data set, consolidating all relevant information across the ten-year period. The Medical Science subject areas data was downloaded into segments due to its large size.

Datasets B was copied from the Scopus intuitive filter interface shown in figure 3.5 while dataset C was retrieved from <https://www.nuc.edu.ng/nigerian-univerisities/federal-univeristies/>, <https://www.nuc.edu.ng/nigerian-univerisities/private-univeristies/>, <https://www.nuc.edu.ng/nigerian-univerisities/state-univerisity/>, and https://www.commonwealthofnations.org/sectors-nigeria/education/research_institutes/ on the 12th March 2025 consecutively. All the collected datasets were loaded into Google Collaboratory for further cleaning and analysis.

Figure 3.1: Basic Search Bar

Figure 3.2 Advanced query Bar

123,296 documents found

All ▾ Export ^ Download Citation overview ... More Show a

	Authors
<input type="checkbox"/> 1 RESULTS IN G-METRIC SPACE	Zeeshan, H.M., Azam, / Shagari, M.S., Bibi, S.

1
 File types
 CSV
 RIS
 BibTeX
 Plain text

[Publisher ↗](#) [Related documents](#)

Figure 3.3 Export options

Export 10 documents to CSV ?

You can export up to 20,000 documents in CSV format.

All documents on this page
 Documents -

What information do you want to export?

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citation information	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Bibliographical information	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Abstract & keywords	<input type="checkbox"/> Funding details
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Author(s)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Affiliations	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Abstract	<input type="checkbox"/> Number
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Document title	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Serial identifiers (e.g. ISSN)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Author keywords	<input type="checkbox"/> Acronym
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Year	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PubMed ID	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Indexed keywords	<input type="checkbox"/> Sponsor
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> EID	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Publisher		<input type="checkbox"/> Funding text
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Source title	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Editor(s)		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Volume, issues, pages	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Language of original document		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Citation count	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Correspondence address		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Source & document type	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Abbreviated source title		
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Publication stage			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DOI			

[Select all information](#) Truncate to optimize for Excel ⓘ Save as preference [Export](#)

Figure 3.4 Export page

Figure 3.5 Scopus Intuitive filter interface

3.6 Organisation and Measurements of the Data

After collection, the aggregation of dataset A resulted in a 36-field/column and 122,898 records/rows dataset as shown in Table 3.1. All the datasets were formatted with the correct datatype showing the variable names for each field, the number of records in each and the corresponding data types. The “object” datatype describes a text or string data while the “int64” refers to integers or whole numbers and “float64” relates to decimal numbers. Specifically, dataset B comprises the names of the 159 countries/territories involved in producing all the publications contained in dataset A and their corresponding regions (within Africa or Outside Africa). Table 3.2 details the structure of the dataset.

Dataset C comprises first, the names of the 274 Nigerian universities found on the NUC website at the time of retrieval, alongside the names of 37 active research institutions in Nigeria found on the commonwealth network website when the data was retrieved. Other details like the institution abbreviation, aliases, institution ownership/funding and the institution type (i.e. university or research institution) were compiled manually from the internet, for most of the institutions, the abbreviations were commonly used in identifying them while for a few, they were inferred. Similarly, the dataset includes the aliases or former names for 116 of these institutions (i.e. “Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University” aliased as “Anambra State University”). Table 3.2 gives an overview of dataset C totaling 311 Nigerian institutions.

Table 3.1: Dataset A. – Metadata of the Research production in Nigeria from 2014 – 2023.

Sn	Column	Count	Data type
1	Authors	122895	object
2	Author full names	122895	object
3	Author(s) ID	122895	object
4	Title	122895	object
5	Year	122898	int64
6	Source title	122898	object
7	Volume	109931	object
8	Issue	84650	object
9	Art. No.	33795	object
10	Page start	85422	object
11	Page end	84073	object
12	Page count	84180	float64
13	Cited by	122898	int64
14	DOI	110074	object
15	Link	122898	object
16	Affiliations	122895	object
17	Authors with affiliations	122895	object
18	Correspondence Address	96121	object
19	Editors	4851	object
20	Publisher	121651	object
21	ISSN	111128	object
22	ISBN	14295	object
23	CODEN	25457	object
24	PubMed ID	26273	float64
25	Language of Original Document	122898	object
26	Abbreviated Source Title	122878	object
27	Document Type	122898	object
28	Publication Stage	122898	object
29	Open Access	58743	object

30	Source	122898	object
31	EID	122898	object
32	Author Keywords	102638	object
33	Index Keywords	68193	object
34	Funding Details	34973	object
35	Funding Texts	34007	object
36	Discipline	122036	object

Table 3.2: Dataset B – Countries/Territories involved in producing the publications in dataset A.

Sn	Column Names	No. of records	Data type
1	Name	159	object
2	Region	159	object

Table 3.3: Dataset C -- Nigerian institution, their abbreviations and aliases.

Sn	Column Names	No. of records	Data type
1	Name	311	object
2	Abbreviation	311	object
3	Funding source	311	object
4	Institution type	311	object
5	Alias/Former name	115	object

3.7 Data Cleaning

Cleaning and transformation of the datasets were necessary for several reasons. Firstly, dataset A comprised all the publications where the keyword “nigeria” appeared anywhere in the publication. This implies that publications written about Nigeria but not affiliated to any Nigerian institutions could be included in it. Also, the data does not provide a single field/column for filtering to determine the county and institutional affiliation, therefore these details need to be extracted for accurate appropriation of affiliation. Lastly, Scopus data, though categorised by subject areas, does not directly include the OECD disciplinary categorisation. Other reasons included the need to categorise dataset B into their geographic regions with respect to Africa. Hence, the datasets were cleaned, transformed and organised accordingly to facilitate the analysis:

3.7.1 Country affiliation extraction

In dataset A, the authors’ country affiliations were stored as a part of the authors’ details in the “*Authors with affiliations*” field (i.e. ‘Niran-atiba T.A., Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Ladoke Akintola University of Technology Teaching Hospital, Osun State, Osogbo, Nigeria’). This data string was extracted into a new field -- “*Countries involved*” in dataset A using a regular expression (RegEx) algorithm that makes use of the country names in dataset B to search and retrieve matching records from dataset A.

3.7.2 Country categorisation into Geographic Regions

The list of countries involved in producing the publications (dataset B) was categorised into their respective regions with Africa as reference point, using conditional logic in python. As a result, countries in Africa were labelled as “*Africa*” while the others were labelled as “*Outside Africa*”

3.7.3 Classification by Collaboration types

In the “*Countries involved*” field extracted earlier, the names of the countries involved were stored together in square brackets, for each of the records, in a separate field i.e. [‘Nigeria’], [‘Nigeria’, ‘South Africa’, ‘United States’], thereby making it possible to examine collaboration types. At this point, dataset A was joined with dataset C based on the “Country involved” column in dataset A and the Names in dataset B, to retrieve the region for each record in dataset A.

Afterward, a new field – “Collaboration type” was created for each record in dataset A to indicate the collaboration type. Collaboration type was implied based on a logical assumption that records where there is only one country involved and the country is Nigeria are local collaborations, whereas publications where only one country was involved, and the region is “*Africa*” are regional collaboration while the rest were labeled as “International” since they involved at least one country outside Africa.

3.7.4 Institutional affiliation extraction

Like the country affiliation extraction, the institutional affiliation was extracted by applying a RegEx algorithm to the “*Authors with affiliations*” column. This algorithm searches the column using the institution names in dataset C as patterns, and then returns the corresponding matches from dataset A. However, before applying the algorithm on dataset A, the institution names in dataset C were cleaned to ensure consistency in both and enhance its suitability for accurate matching

Using the simple name matching, only a few of the institutions in dataset C had corresponding matches in dataset. Further inspection reveals that the limited matches were largely due to the difference in the naming convention i.e. “University of Nigeria” and

“University of Nigeria, Nsukka”. Although a few others were affiliated institutions that were not recognised as institutions on their own i.e. “College of Medicine, University of Ibadan” and “University of Ibadan. To resolve the misalignments, the aliases were also used in the extraction algorithm to handle some naming convention differences, making the algorithm more robust for matching. Also, the parent institutions’ names were used to replace the affiliated institutions names, merging their records.

3.7.5 OECD Classification of Disciplines

To facilitate the disciplinary analysis, the Scopus subject area classifications (i.e. “Environmental Science”, “Materials Science”, “Economics, Econometrics and Finance”.) were added as field labels for each record in the dataset following the segmented download. This field was then further categorised into the OECD’s six broad disciplines to reduce the number of disciplines, guided by the OECD Frascati manual 2015 (Figure 3.6) adapted from Asubiaro, (2023). Upon the data organisation and transformation, the final dataset is displayed in Table 3.4

Table 3.4: Final dataset variables

Sn	Column	Count	Data type
1	EID	122891	object
2	Authors with affiliations	122891	object
3	Year	122891	int64
4	Countries involved	122891	object
5	Region	122891	object
6	Collaboration Type	122891	object
7	Institutions involved	97659	object
8	Abbreviation	97029	object
9	Funding	97213	object
10	Institution type	97544	object

11	Discipline	121331	object
12	OECD Class	121331	object

Broad classification	Second-level classification
1. Natural sciences	1.1 Mathematics 1.2 Computer and information sciences 1.3 Physical sciences 1.4 Chemical sciences 1.5 Earth and related environmental sciences 1.6 Biological sciences 1.7 Other natural sciences
2. Engineering and technology	2.1 Civil engineering 2.2 Electrical engineering, electronic engineering, information engineering 2.3 Mechanical engineering 2.4 Chemical engineering 2.5 Materials engineering 2.6 Medical engineering 2.7 Environmental engineering 2.8 Environmental biotechnology 2.9 Industrial biotechnology 2.10 Nano-technology 2.11 Other engineering and technologies
3. Medical and health sciences	3.1 Basic medicine 3.2 Clinical medicine 3.3 Health sciences 3.4 Medical biotechnology 3.5 Other medical science
4. Agricultural and veterinary sciences	4.1 Agriculture, forestry, and fisheries 4.2 Animal and dairy science 4.3 Veterinary science 4.4 Agricultural biotechnology 4.5 Other agricultural sciences
5. Social sciences	5.1 Psychology and cognitive sciences 5.2 Economics and business 5.3 Education 5.4 Sociology 5.5 Law 5.6 Political science 5.7 Social and economic geography 5.8 Media and communications 5.9 Other social sciences
6. Humanities and the arts	6.1 History and archaeology 6.2 Languages and literature 6.3 Philosophy, ethics and religion 6.4 Arts (arts, history of arts, performing arts, music) 6.5 Other humanities

Figure 3.6 OECD Disciplinary Classification (OECD 2015, p. 59)

3.8 Data Analysis

Following the data organisation, the following analyses were conducted to achieve the study's objectives:

1. **Publication Trend and Growth:** to quantifying the number of publications in Nigeria, the number of publications produced by the researchers affiliated with Nigerian institutions each year from 2014 to 2023 was counted. A trend analysis was performed to identify any significant changes in research output over the period while the annual publication counts were visualised using line graphs and bar charts to illustrate trends and patterns in research productivity. The year-on-year growth rate in publications was calculated, and the correlation between Collaboration Level and growth in research output was analysed. Keyword analysis will also feature to understand the common themes in research output.
2. **Institutional Analysis:** In comparing the research productivity across institutions, publication counts were aggregated at the institutional level to assess the research productivity of different Nigerian universities and research institutions. The publication count of medical affiliations was merged with their parent institutions to improve the summarisation. i.e. University college hospital, Ibadan's records were merged with the University of Ibadan etc. The top performing institutions were identified based on their publication counts. Factors contributing to high research productivity, such as institutional type and funding sources, were examined. The research output of the top institutions was visualised using bar charts, with further analysis conducted into collaboration types and institutional characteristics.

3. **Discipline Classification:** To examine research productivity by discipline, publications were classified according to the OECD's six discipline categories. This classification allowed for an analysis of research productivity at the discipline level. The data were analysed to identify disciplines with the highest and lowest research output. Trends within each discipline were examined to uncover areas of strength and potential improvement. The distribution of research productivity across disciplines was visualised using bar charts and heatmaps.
4. **Collaboration Analysis:** to analyse the impact of collaboration, the dataset was examined to determine the distribution of publications by Collaboration Level (local, regional, and international). Also, collaboration metrics like the Collaboration Index (CI) (Lawani, 1980), Degree of Collaboration (DC) (Subramanyam, 1983), Collaboration Co-efficient (CC) (Ajiferuke et al., 1988), and the Modified Collaboration Coefficient (MCC) (Savanur et al., 2010) were examined. The findings were presented using VoS Viewer, a network analysis tool that visualised and quantified the strength of collaborations, allowing for a detailed examination of the collaboration networks. This included an analysis of how many times Nigerian institutions collaborated with specific foreign institutions. Additionally, bar charts and line graphs were utilised to highlight differences in research productivity across different collaboration levels.
5. **Lotka's law:** we tested Lotka's law on the dataset by assessing the frequency of publication per author in each year and visualising the data on charts to confirm if it follows the Power law rule

3.9 Ethical Considerations

The study handled data in a manner that respected privacy and confidentiality. All data used was publicly available bibliometric data, and no personal or sensitive information was processed. The analysis was conducted following ethical research practices, ensuring transparency and integrity in data handling and reporting. Additionally, ethical approval was not applicable for this study, as human subjects were not involved in a way that could create potential harm.

3.10 Limitations

Some limitations of this study included the reliance on Scopus as the main data source for determining research production. This may have limited the inclusiveness of the research as not all the publications of authors affiliated with Nigerian institutions are indexed in Scopus. Additionally, the categorisation of research outputs into OECD disciplines could introduce bias if certain publications were misclassified from the source data on Scopus.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the analysis and findings from the data collected, addressing the five research objectives outlined in chapter one. It includes summaries of the collected data, statistical treatments, and the outcomes of each objective, illustrated through tables and figures. The purpose is to provide a clear and organised presentation of findings, highlighting trends, patterns, and insights from the research data.

4.2 Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question One: What is the quantity of publications produced by researchers affiliated with Nigerian Institutions between 2014 and 2023 and what are the trends in research productivity?

4.2.1 Research Productivity Trends and Growth

The first part of this objective is the quantity of publications produced by researchers affiliated with Nigerian institutions between 2014 and 2023 is 122,891. This number was determined by summing the number of unique publications in the dataset. In the Scopus database, publications are assigned unique electronic identifiers called the ‘*eid*’ (i.e. “2-s2.0-85085406167”), counting the number of unique identifiers in the dataset gave an accurate sum of the total publications, although counting the number of unique Digital Object identifiers (DOIs) could be an alternative.

Figure 4.1 shows the annual publication trend, revealing a steep rise in the productivity of Nigerian researchers from year 2015 until in 2021 when the increase became only marginal. Remarkably, a massive increase in research productivity was recorded during this period. Other trends observed in the productivity of Nigerian researchers over the 10-year period include the Year-over-Year (YoY) growth and the Compound Yearly Growth Rate (CAGR), also referred to as the Total Publication Growth (TPG).

Figure 4.1: Annual Publications trend

The yearly breakdown of publications from Nigeria alongside the YoY growth rate are shown in Table 4.1. The YoY growth refers to the change in research production from one year to another, a huge 26.46% being the maximum yearly growth, recorded in 2019. It indicates a fall or rise in productivity between two specific years, and it is calculated as shown in the Figure 4.2. Where α is the YoY, measured as a percentage. CV refers to the number of publications in the current year considered and PV is the number of publications in the year preceding the current year. For example, the CV and PV for calculating the YoY growth for year 2017 were the publication counts for 2017 and 2016, which were 8,450 and 7,395 publications, producing a 14.27% growth.

$$\alpha = \left(\left(\frac{CV - PV}{PV} \right) \times 100 \right)$$

Figure 4.2: Year-Over-Year growth formula

Table 4.1: Yearly Publications and Growth Rate

Year	Annual Publication	Annual Growth Rate (%)
2014	6,442	-
2015	6,419	-0.36
2016	7,395	15.20
2017	8,450	14.27
2018	10,269	21.53
2019	12,986	26.46
2020	15,415	18.70
2021	18,027	16.94
2022	18,282	1.41
2023	19,206	5.05
Total	122,891	

Figure 4.3 represents a visualisation of the YoY growth on a line chart. The graphic reveals the two segmentations of growth within this ten-year period A rocky growth rate within the first five years which ended in 2019 and a reluctant decline in the second half, except for the period between 2022 and 2023.

Figure 4.3: Year-Over-Year (YOY) Growth (2014–2023)

Also, the Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of Nigeria’s research output reveals a growth of approximately **11.54%** between 2014 and 2023. The compound annual growth rate (CAGR) represents the total growth rate within this period. The formular for calculating this is shown on figure 4.4, where is δ is the CAGR is measured as a percentage, LY refers to the Last Value, that is number of publications in the final year 2023, FY is the First Value which is the number of publications in the first year 2014, and n is the number of years considered, which in this case, is ten.

$$\delta = \left(\left(\left(\frac{LV}{FY} \right)^{1/n} - 1 \right) \times 100 \right)$$

Figure 4.4: Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR)

$$\delta = \left(\left(\left(\frac{19206}{6442} \right)^{1/10} - 1 \right) \times 100 \right)$$

$$\delta = \left(\left((2.981372245)^{0.1} - 1 \right) \times 100 \right)$$

$$\delta = \left((1.115428201 - 1) \times 100 \right)$$

$$\delta = (0.115428201 \times 100)$$

$$\delta \simeq 11.54\%$$

Research Question Two: What are the distributions of authorship in Nigeria’s research outputs.

Table 4.2 presents a frequency distribution showing the authorship distribution per year, from 2014 to 2023. Out of the 653,363 authors, an overwhelming 604,238 (92.4%) published only once during the observed period. Similarly, 36,629 (5.6%) published exactly two publications, and only 6,881 (1.05%) produced three publications during the observed period. As the number of publications per author increases, the dataset reveals a steep drop in frequency. Researchers, with at least four publications contribute a significantly smaller portion of the overall output, with only less than 5,615 (0.85%) of them throughout the ten years.

The most exceptional cases of productivity appear in the extreme upper range. The dataset records a single researcher with 107 publications, making them the most prolific author in Nigeria during the study period. Additionally, only one researcher produced 62 publications, while a few others contributed between 35 and 43 papers over the decade. These highly productive researchers represent an exceptionally small fraction of the total academic population. The full distribution is presented in Table 8. Likewise, the distributions charts for the entire period and the five-year periods are shown in figures 4.11 to 4.13 while the annual authorship distributions charts are included in appendix III.

Table 4.2: Authorship Frequency Table

Publication Count	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Grand Total
1	26,014	29,473	34,392	40,592	48,594	58,179	69,152	95,305	98,907	103,630	604,238
2	1,087	1,317	2,020	2,791	2,767	3,482	4,454	5,797	6,265	6,649	36,629
3	217	222	503	528	550	618	818	958	1,186	1,281	6,881
4	47	69	167	215	194	205	306	418	366	478	2,465
5	21	21	92	95	115	83	152	296	185	232	1,292
6	13	8	40	40	86	43	86	81	125	124	646
7	2	4	28	35	43	29	56	53	56	50	356
8	4	3	11	17	43	8	44	43	29	50	252
9	1		12	18	10	10	28	18	24	34	155
10			6	15	7	7	10	20	18	27	110
11	1	2	1	4	5	4	17	11	15	13	73
12	2		1	7	3	3	8	4	12	6	46
13		1	3	1	5		10	6	3	9	38
14	1			2	1		4	9	4	6	27
15				1	1	1	3	3	6	10	25
16	1	12	1				3	2	4	9	32
17	1		1	3			3	2	3	1	14
18					2				4		6
19					2		4	1		2	9
20					1	1	1			2	5
21					1		2	2	2	1	8
22					1			1	1	2	5
23	1							1	1		3
24						1	1			1	3
25								1		1	2

26									2	1	3
27						1	1	2		5	9
28							1		2	4	7
29							1	3	2	3	9
31										1	1
32								3			3
33								2			2
34								1			1
35									1		1
36										1	1
38										1	1
42								1	1		2
43										1	1
62										1	1
107										1	1
Grand Total	27,413	31,132	37,278	44,364	52,431	62,675	75,165	103,044	107,224	112,637	653,363

The author who published 107 papers in 2023 was Keebayoon, A. identified as, a private academic consultant in Cambodia. He also holds many other academic positions in different institutions in other countries, including an Adjunct Professor affiliated to Joseph Ayo Babalola University, Nigeria. Keebayoon/Klebayoon is neither a lead author nor a sole author in any of the 107 papers. He is also not available in any of the Academic Social Networking Websites such as ResearchGate or in Academic Search Engines such as Google Scholar. Also, Professor C.O Adetunji of the Department of Microbiology, Edo State University who published 62 papers in 2023. Professor Adetunji's Google Scholar page shows his numerous publications, a citation of about 10,000. He also has an h-Index of 42 overall. He is a Professor

of Microbiology Biotechnology and Nanotechnology. In addition, Misra S. of the Covenant University and Olarinoye I.O. of the department of Physics, Federal University of Technology Minna, were the scholars responsible for publishing 42 papers each in 2021 and 2022 respectively.

4.2.2 Authorship Distribution from 2014 to 2023

Figure 4.5 illustrates the relationship between the number of publications and the number of authors from 2014 to 2023. The graph shows a sharp decrease in the number of authors as the number of publications increases. Specifically, a very high number of authors is observed for a low number of publications, and this number drops drastically as the number of publications increases, eventually plateauing at a low number of authors for a high number of publications.

Figure 4.5: Overall Authorship distribution

4.2.3 Authorship Distribution (2014 to 2018)

The first five-year period, spanning from 2014 to 2018, saw a consistent increase in research productivity. A key characteristic of this period was the dominance of single-publication authors. Researchers who published only once accounted for most contributions, 179,065 authors (93%) originating from this category. Also, multi-publication authors were present, but their numbers remained relatively low. Figure 4.6 shows only 2,020 publications came from authors with three works, while those with five or more publications accounted for just 859 contributions over the five years. The researcher with the highest number of publications in this period had a staggering 27 publications during the year 2019.

Figure 4.6: Authorship distributions (2014 to 2018)

4.2.4 Authorship Distribution (2019 to 2023)

The second five-year period, covering 2019 to 2023, marked a significant acceleration in research productivity. The total number of authors in this period reached 398,070, more than double the total output from the previous five-year period, publishing 83,916 publications. A notable observation in this period was the marginal deflection of single researchers into multi-publication researchers (see Figure 4.7). While single-publication authors still accounted for most contributions (425,173 or 92.3%), the number of researchers with sustained productivity grew significantly. Authors with three or more publications are 4,861 while the highest number of publications by a single researcher rose dramatically to 107.

Figure 4.7: Authorship Distributions (2019 to 2023)

Research Question Three: What are the patterns of collaboration in Nigeria’s research outputs, focusing on the collaboration types and levels.

To determine the collaboration patterns, the publications were categorised by collaboration types, that is local (within Nigeria), regional (within Africa), and international (outside Africa), based on author affiliations. This classification helps determine if different types of collaboration correlate with higher productivity. The categorisation in Table 4.3 indicates that 64,360 publications which accounted for about 52% of the publications involved Local collaboration, the regional collaboration represents 9% of the research output (11,238 publications), while 39% (47,273) are international collaborations.

Table 4.3: Distribution across the collaborations type

Collaboration Type	Number of publications	Percentage %
Local	64,360	52
International	47,273	39
Regional	11,238	9

Drilling further, the visualisation chart in Figure 4.8, showing the trend based on the type of collaboration, indicates that international collaborations have been on the rise although significantly below local collaborations. But local collaborations began decreasing in 2021 and were eventually overtaken by international collaborations in the year 2022, yet well above regional collaborations.

Figure 4.8: Publication trend of the different Collaboration types

4.2.5 International Collaborations

Furthermore, exploring trends in collaboration helped to identify the top 20 of the 158 countries collaborating with Nigeria, as shown on a bar chart in Figure 4.9. The most frequent partners are South Africa and the United States, which accounted for a considerable portion of international collaborations. Other key partners included the United Kingdom, Malaysia, India and China, showing that Nigeria's research network spans across multiple continents. Collaborations with the United States and United Kingdom represents over 66% of Nigeria's co-authored publications. South Africa ranks as the top African collaborator, with a high number of joint publications. Table 4.4 shows the collaborating countries and their publication records while the full details are included in appendix I.

Figure 4.9: Top 20 Collaborating Countries with Nigeria

Figure 4.10: Network Map of Nigeria’s Collaborating Countries

The network map (Figure 4.10) from VOSviewer shows Nigeria’s international research collaborations with various countries. Nigeria is represented as a large node or circle, indicating its central position in this network, with strong links to the United Kingdom, South Africa, and the United States. This strengthens the finding that positions South Africa, United States and the United Kingdom as the top collaborating countries with Nigeria. Clusters of smaller nodes connected to Nigeria reflect collaborations with other African countries (like Ghana, Uganda) and countries outside Africa (such as China, Malaysia, and India). The colour-coded clusters suggest regional patterns, where Nigeria collaborates more with countries within specific networks, potentially based on historical, linguistic, or regional ties.

4.2.6 Collaborations and Author Productivity

Figure 4.11 depicts the co-authorship network map in Nigerian research. The map identifies top individuals and co-authors using a threshold of at least seven co-authored papers due to the large size of participating authors. Table 4.4 lists the top 20 most prolific authors while the full list is included in appendix II. The leading author is Wiwanitkit V. with 167 publications, followed by Ozili P.K., with 58 publications, followed closely by Loto R.T. (52 publications). Other notable authors include Oyelude A.A. (37 publications) and Idumah C.I. (35 publications). In addition to these individual prolific authors, there are notable co-authorship pairs with high publication counts. These include Kleebayoon A. & Wiwanitkit V.

Figure 4.11 Author Collaboration Network Map

(157 publications), Joob B. & Wiwanitkit V. (142 publications), and Mungmunpantipantip R. & Wiwanitkit V. (107 publications).

Examining the individual profile of some of these authors, Viroj Wiwanitkit, the most productive scholar, who, despite not being Nigerian, has published extensively in connection with Nigeria. His institutional affiliation is Patil University, India. Also, Kleebayoon A., as earlier noted, is affiliated with Joseph Ayo Babalola University as an Adjunct Professor. His collaboration with Wiwanitkit suggests a strong research synergy in global public health concerns, particularly those relevant to tropical regions like Nigeria.

Among Nigerian authors, Ozili P.K. is affiliated with ESCP Business School, France, specialising in finance, banking, and economic policy. His publication pattern indicates a mix of solo research and co-authored works, collaborating with both local and international scholars. Loto R.T. is a researcher at Covenant University, Nigeria, focusing his research on corrosion inhibition, material properties, and protective coatings, addressing challenges in engineering and industrial applications. Oyelude A.A., affiliated with University of Ilorin, Nigeria, contributes significantly to library and information science, covering topics such as library management, digital literacy, academic publishing trends, and information access in Nigeria.

Table 4.4: Top 20 most prolific individual and co-authors

Sn	Label	Cluster	Links	Documents	Citations	Norm. citations	Avg. pub. year	Avg. citations	Avg. norm. citations
1	wiwanitkit v.	248.00	0.00	167	179	10.25	2016	1.07	0.06
2	kleebayoon a.; wiwanitkit v.	145.00	0.00	157	262	98.83	2023	1.67	0.63
3	joob b.; wiwanitkit v.	140.00	0.00	142	196	11.01	2017	1.38	0.08

4	mungmunpantip r.; wiwanitkit v.	159.00	0.00	107	108	21.08	2022	1.01	0.20
5	sookaromdee p.; wiwanitkit v.	231.00	0.00	62	51	8.71	2022	0.82	0.14
6	ozili p.k.	222.00	0.00	58	888	145.53	2022	15.31	2.51
7	loto r.t.	152.00	0.00	52	515	30.01	2019	9.90	0.58
8	wiwanitkit s.; wiwanitkit v.	247.00	0.00	51	55	2.74	2016	1.08	0.05
9	yasri s.; wiwanitkit v.	250.00	0.00	48	26	2.21	2018	0.54	0.05
10	oyelude a.a.	219.00	0.00	37	128	9.93	2019	3.46	0.27
11	idumah c.i.	115.00	0.00	35	1129	228.72	2022	32.26	6.54
12	emetere m.e.	93.00	0.00	33	161	9.68	2018	4.88	0.29
13	owolabi k.m.	215.00	0.00	29	866	54.78	2019	29.86	1.89
14	omodero c.o.	203.00	0.00	28	155	13.35	2021	5.54	0.48
15	amah o.e.	53.00	0.00	26	130	12.38	2022	5.00	0.48
16	kalantar-zadeh k.; li p.k.-t.; tantisattamo e.; kumaraswami l.; liakopoulos v.; lui s.-f.; ulasi i.; andreoli s.; balducci a.; dupuis s.; harris t.; hradsky a.; knight r.; kumar s.; ng m.; poidevin a.; saadi g.; tong a.	142.00	0.00	26	46	4.82	2021	1.77	0.19
17	mahamood r.m.; akinlabi e.t.	155.00	0.00	26	599	28.81	2017	23.04	1.11
18	abbasi k.; ali p.; barbour v.; benfield t.; bibbins-domingo k.; erhabor g.e.; hancocks s.; horton r.; laybourn-langton l.; mash r.; sahani p.; sharief w.m.; yonga p.; zielinski c.	1.00	0.00	25	7	2.65	2023	0.28	0.11
19	nnolim u.a.	165	0.00	25	227	15.00	2019	9.08	0.60

20	li p.k.-t.; garcia-garcia g.; lui s.-f.; andreoli s.; fung w.w.-s.; hradsky a.; kumaraswami l.; liakopoulos v.; rakhimova z.; ...	149	0.00	23	173	12.71	2020	7.52	0.55
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4.2.7 Trends in Collaboration Levels

Table 4.5 presents a cross-section of the collaboration levels for each year. The total number of published research papers increased steadily from 6,442 in 2014 to 19,206 in 2023. Single-author publications, although significant, show a declining trend relative to multi-author collaborations. The number of papers with a single author fluctuated, reaching a peak of 1,651 in 2021 before decreasing to 1,339 in 2023. The most common research collaborations involved two to five authors, representing about 62.5% of the collaborated publications. The number of two-author papers increased from 1,437 in 2014 to 2,477 in 2023, while three-author publications grew from 1,359 to 2,975 over the same period. Similarly, four-author and five-author collaborations experienced growth, reaching 3,014 and 2,390 respectively in 2023.

Table 4.5: Collaboration Level per year

Author Count	Publication per year											
	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Grand Total	% Total
1	904	836	891	959	1007	1199	1444	1651	1293	1339	11523	9.38%
2	1437	1288	1406	1489	1702	2173	2392	2568	2270	2477	19202	15.63%
3	1359	1434	1602	1706	2078	2594	3014	3189	2978	2975	22929	18.66%
4	981	1005	1188	1447	1764	2254	2571	2931	3044	3014	20199	16.44%

5	638	616	752	937	1199	1626	1823	2171	2318	2390	14470	11.77%
6	413	444	488	645	887	1147	1402	1666	1862	1926	10880	8.85%
7	215	234	288	352	505	598	803	1048	1206	1266	6515	5.30%
8	130	143	181	244	291	422	506	714	833	909	4373	3.56%
9	72	87	134	158	206	226	335	461	581	627	2887	2.35%
10	58	64	93	113	134	171	259	342	393	536	2163	1.76%
11	47	44	51	66	72	96	138	220	243	325	1302	1.06%
12	29	36	42	50	55	70	114	159	240	248	1043	0.85%
13	17	30	37	34	43	50	113	132	131	159	746	0.61%
14	17	19	31	17	38	50	60	87	104	167	590	0.48%
15	11	12	29	21	38	33	45	71	83	117	460	0.37%
16	8	13	17	12	22	30	25	56	63	86	332	0.27%
17	10	9	14	11	24	14	29	42	47	68	268	0.22%
18	7	9	8	11	11	15	28	71	37	44	241	0.20%
19	3	6	8	13	10	13	20	36	48	37	194	0.16%
20	9	5	9	9	11	11	25	31	26	47	183	0.15%
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
570	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.00%
571	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0.00%
576	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0.00%
581	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.00%
584	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	2	0.00%
587	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.00%
588	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0.00%

595	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.00%
599	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.00%
607	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	0.00%
621	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0.00%
626	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.00%
643	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0.00%
667	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0.00%
680	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0.00%
700	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0.00%
747	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.00%
953	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0.00%
1057	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0.00%
1060	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.00%
Grand Total	6442	6419	7395	8450	10269	12986	15415	18027	18282	19206	122891	

Papers with six to ten authors showed a steady rise, reflecting broader team-based research efforts. For example, six-author publications grew from 413 in 2014 to 1,926 in 2023, while ten-author collaborations rose from 58 to 536. Although less frequent, large-scale collaborations involving more than ten authors also increased. Eleven-author publications rose from 47 in 2014 to 325 in 2023, while those with 15 or more authors, though still rare, also exhibited growth.

An intriguing observation in the dataset is the presence of research articles with an exceptionally high number of coauthors. The most extreme cases include papers with over 500 authors, with the highest recorded numbers being 1,060 and 1057 authors in 2018 and 2019 respectively.

The article with 1060 authors was published in 2018 was “The African Surgical Outcomes Study (ASOS)” which addressed the case surgical patients in Africa experiencing a mortality rate twice the global average. Recognising that existing risk assessment tools are not tailored to the African context, researchers aimed to develop a simple, preoperative risk stratification tool - the ASOS Surgical Risk Calculator - to identify African surgical patients at risk for in-hospital postoperative mortality and severe complications. This tool was derived from a 7-day prospective cohort study involving 8,799 adult patients across 168 African hospitals. Researchers employed a multivariable logistic regression model to identify key preoperative risk factors, including age, ASA physical status, indication for surgery, urgency, severity, and type of surgery. The model demonstrated good discrimination with an area under the receiver operating characteristic curve of 0.805 and good calibration with a c-statistic corrected for optimism of 0.784.

Similarly, the article with 1057 authors relates to an extension of the ASOS study of 2018. It was a “Maternal and neonatal outcomes after caesarean delivery in the African Surgical Outcomes Study”. The African Surgical Outcomes Study (ASOS) conducted a 7-day prospective observational cohort study to assess maternal and neonatal outcomes following caesarean deliveries in Africa. The study included 3,792 patients undergoing caesarean delivery across 183 hospitals in 22 African countries. The findings revealed a maternal

mortality rate of 5.43 per 1,000 operations, which is significantly higher than the global average. Additionally, 9.2% of women experienced severe maternal outcomes, and 14.6% of neonates had adverse outcomes. The study identified several risk factors associated with poor maternal outcomes, including obstetric hemorrhage, anesthesia complications, etc. These results highlight the urgent need for improved perioperative care and resources to enhance maternal and neonatal outcomes in African settings.

4.2.8 Collaboration Metrics

The Collaboration level in Nigerian research was assessed using three key indicators: the Collaborative Index (CI), the Degree of Collaboration (DC), and the Collaborative Coefficient (CC). These metrics offer a multidimensional perspective on how researchers in Nigeria have engaged in collaborative efforts over the years. The Collaborative Index (CI), which represents the average number of authors per paper, reveals a significant upward trend over the examined period (2014–2023). From Table 4.6, the CI stood at 4.56 in 2014 but steadily increased, reaching 6.64 in 2023. Then a notable jump in CI occurred in 2021 (6.41), followed by further increments in 2022 (6.57) and 2023 (6.64), marking a peak in collaborative activity.

Table 4.6: Comparison of Collaboration Metrics

Year	CI	DC	CC
2014	4.559143	0.859671	0.001409
2015	5.215921	0.869762	0.001922
2016	5.660041	0.879513	0.002144
2017	5.948047	0.886509	0.001581
2018	5.723245	0.901938	0.001518
2019	5.319806	0.907670	0.000831
2020	5.512099	0.906325	0.000440

2021	6.406058	0.908415	0.000637
2022	6.572859	0.929275	0.000448
2023	6.639019	0.930282	0.000438

The Degree of Collaboration (DC) provides additional insight by measuring the proportion of multi-authored papers. A DC value close to 1 suggests that nearly all publications involve multiple authors, while lower values indicate a stronger presence of single author works. In 2014, the DC value was 0.86, already indicating a strong culture of co-authorship. Over the years, this trend intensified, with DC reaching 0.93 in 2023. This means that by the end of the period, over 93% of all publications were written by multiple authors. Interestingly, the sharp rise in DC from 2021 onward aligns with the period of increasing CI values.

The Collaborative Coefficient (CC) provides a more robust picture by accounting for both single and multi-authored works. Unlike the previous two metrics, a lower CC value indicates a stronger tendency toward collaboration. Over the years, the CC values remained very low. In 2014, the CC stood at 0.00141 and increased slightly in 2015 (0.00192), then peaked in 2016 (0.00214). From 2017 to 2019, the CC values showed a downward trend, decreasing from 0.00158 in 2017 to 0.00083 in 2019. The years following 2019 witnessed a dramatic decline in CC, reaching the lowest values in the dataset. By 2020, CC had dropped to 0.00044, and this trend continued in 2021 (0.00064), 2022 (0.00045), and 2023 (0.00044). The trend visualised in Figure 4.12 revealed a sharp and dipping drop in CC since 2019.

Figure 4.12: Yearly Trend of the Collaborative Coefficient

Research Objective Four: What are the predominant fields/disciplines of research (OECD discipline areas) among Nigerian authors, and how does publication trends vary across these fields?

As part of the goal stated in previous chapters, this study dug deeper to understand the strengths and weakness in Nigerian research in order to identify potential opportunities for growth, and hence conducted a field level analysis based the six OECD disciplinary areas, namely, Natural Sciences (NatSc), Medical and Health Sciences (M&Hsc), Social Sciences (SocSc), Engineering and Technology (E&Tech.), Agricultural and Veterinary Sciences (Ag&VetSc), and Humanities and the Arts (H&A). Of the 122,891 publications, 4 publications were classified as ‘undefined’ and was hence, excluded from the analysis since their number is negligible. When categorised by the OECD disciplines, Figure 4.13 depicted the distribution. M&Hsc achieved the highest number of publications with 37,943 publication, followed by the rest in order, NatSc (27,994), SocSc (23,872), E&Tech (23,872), Ag&VetSc (14,402), H&A (626).

Figure 4.13: Disciplinary distribution by OECD discipline

4.2.9 Publication trend across the OECD Disciplines

Additionally, from the disciplinary publication trend in Figure 4.14, we observe growth across all disciplines with each having their different peak years. For example, NatSc discipline enjoyed a one year lead between 2018 and 2019 after which it was overtaken by M&Hsc owing to the former's spiky growth where the later maintained a steady growth. Furthermore, the trend reveals a pairwise contest among the disciplines. M&Hsc versus NatSc and; SocSc versus E&Tech; with Ag&VetSc and H&A scarcely contending in the league. The full trend details are included in Table 4.7.

Figure 4.14: Publication Trend by OECD Disciplines

Table 4.7 Annual Productivity trend across disciplines

Year	OECD Discipline						
	Medical and health sciences	Natural sciences	Engineering and technology	Agricultural and veterinary sciences	Social sciences	Multidisciplinary	Humanities and the arts
2014	2431	1056	1065	907	764	83	15
2015	2348	1229	1141	835	634	79	13
2016	2432	1582	1353	1046	709	131	11
2017	2550	1902	1681	1164	855	130	31
2018	2839	2330	2178	1457	895	361	29
2019	3318	3236	3079	1492	1101	407	41
2020	4840	3454	2918	1670	1386	769	48
2021	5511	4741	3137	1928	1647	763	114
2022	5747	4308	3442	1987	1696	704	157
2023	5927	4156	3878	1916	1812	883	167
Grand Total	37943	27994	23872	14402	11499	4310	626

4.2.10 Collaboration types across the OECD disciplines

The productivity across the OECD disciplines was also examined based on their Collaboration types as shown in Table 4.8, and the analysis unveiled a few findings. One is that across disciplines, local collaboration is the top driver of research productivity while regional collaboration is generally lower compared to other collaboration levels. Another is the Humanities and Arts unlike the other disciplines tend to engage more in international collaboration.

Table 4.8: Disciplinary Productivity across Collaboration Types

OECD Discipline	Collaboration Type		
	International	Local	Regional
Medical and health sciences	15980	19426	2537
Natural sciences	10216	15024	2754
Engineering and technology	9552	11803	2517
Agricultural and veterinary sciences	5381	7566	1455
Social sciences	3051	7361	1087
Multidisciplinary	1720	2105	485
Humanities and the arts	372	186	68

Research Objective Five: Who are high-performing (top 10) institutions and what are their institutional features and productivity per discipline?

Out of the 311 Nigerian institutions compiled for the study, only 236 produced at least one publication within this period while the rest did not record any publication within this period (although about 12.8% of the entire records did not match any name on our list of Nigerian institutions). The data shows that within the 10-year period under consideration, the University of Nigeria, Nsukka and University of Ibadan led in publication counts with 13,122 and 13,078 publications respectively. Followed closely by the Covenant university and University of Lagos, also producing 7,799 and 6,843 respectively. On the whole, the top ten institutions accounted for a significant majority (about 62%) of Nigeria’s research productivity, with publication counts ranging from approximately 3,562 to 13,122 across these institutions as shown in Figure 4.15.

Figure 4.15: Productivity of Top Ten Nigerian Institutions

4.2.11 Institutional Features of the Top Ten institutions

The funding type and institution type were the two characteristics of the top ten institutions examined. The analysis unveils two major funding sources of high performing institutions, the federal government, and private institutions. The federal government funded over 90% (57,516) of the publications while only a private university (Covenant University) produced the remaining 10% (77,99 publications). Institution type on the other hand shows that the research space in Nigeria is dominated by the universities only with not research institution making the list.

4.2.12 Publication trends of Top Ten Nigerian Institutions

Figure 4.16 reveals a growth in the publication trends analysis of the top ten institutions, with notable peaks during specific years. University of Ibadan and University of Lagos showed a consistent upward trend, with remarkable increases since 2018. Covenant University, however, displayed a sharp rise from 2019. The publication counts per year for each of the top institutions highlights the growth trends and fluctuations over time, with almost all of them experiencing decline in productivity in 2021, breakdown is shown in Table 4.9.

Table 4.9: Yearly research output of the top Nigerian institutions

Sn	Institutions involved	Yearly publication										
		2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Grand Total
1	University of Ibadan	807	804	958	1046	1163	1286	1660	1903	1730	1765	13122
2	University of Nigeria	566	589	667	754	924	1380	1702	2113	2156	2226	13077
3	Covenant University	229	322	447	618	1206	1506	988	1053	873	557	7799

4	University of Lagos	376	404	416	523	667	690	841	947	992	987	6843
5	Obafemi Awolowo University	411	424	489	616	620	663	791	896	926	936	6772
6	University of Ilorin	333	278	318	433	522	649	821	971	1035	984	6344
7	Ahmadu Bello University	305	299	317	344	422	565	637	755	793	883	5320
8	Federal University of Technology, Akure	177	176	235	296	403	481	528	684	602	549	4131
9	Bayero University	146	198	195	219	311	431	511	678	611	612	3912
10	University of Benin	260	273	212	272	308	325	440	496	495	481	3562

Figure 4.16: Publication Trend Analysis by Institutions

4.2.13 Collaboration trends of top ten Nigerian institutions

On collaboration patterns, the top institutions have distinct collaboration patterns, with a higher tendency for international partnerships in certain universities compared to others. Predominantly, except for Bayero university that has a relatively lower number, local collaborations are the most dominant collaboration type among the top ten institutions. Also, University of Nigeria and University of Ibadan exhibited a relatively balanced distribution across local, regional, and international collaborations. Figure 4.17 compares the collaboration levels (local, regional, and international) for each top institution and reveals how collaboration patterns vary by institution.

Figure 4.17: Collaboration types of Top Ten Institutions

To further gain insight into where collaboration efforts are most concentrated and to highlight institutions' relative strengths, a heatmap (Figure 4.18) was plotted to visualise the intensity of collaborations by institution and collaboration types. Institutions are plotted on the y-axis, while collaboration types (local, regional, international) are on the x-axis. The colour intensity represents the frequency of publications for each collaboration type at each institution. The heatmap emphasises the University of Ibadan and University of Nigeria as the leaders in international collaboration. It also exposes Bayero University's productivity as being majorly driven by international collaborations.

Figure 4.18: Heat Map of Collaboration for the Top Ten institutions

The analysis in Figure 4.19 extends the one above to prevent bias or misinterpretation that may occur in determining collaboration strength based on only the publication counts. Basically, the chart computed the same numbers in Figure 4.18 as a percentage of the total publication per institution. The results revealed that while the University of Ibadan leads by the number of publications across the collaboration types, Bayero University's strength is rooted in international collaboration, having about 57% of its publication involving international partnerships, followed by Amadu Bello university (39.9%).

Also, it is clearer that University of Benin has the biggest influence in local collaboration with a percentage of 64.1% of its total publication with the 10-year period while Covenant University (CU) has some more focused regional collaboration than the other institutions, having 15% of its research productions because of regional collaboration.

Figure 4.19: Percentage of Collaboration for the Top Ten Institutions

4.2.14 Disciplinary Productivity of top ten institutions

Since the disciplinary area was introduced, the analysis also explored the capacity of the top ten institutions by the disciplinary areas as seen in Figure 4.20. This exploration made it clear that while the M&Hsc discipline contributed the largest number of publications across all institutions (Figure 4.13), it also appear to represent the main strengths of the top institutions in Nigeria. Likewise, the other fields maintained their respective positions.

Figure 4.20: Productivity of Top Ten Institutions across Discipline

However, while these fields maintained the same overall positions among the top ten institutions, the case is not the same in the individual institutions. Table 4.10 clearly shows that each institution has its peculiar research strengths and weaknesses. UI led the M&Hsc field with a total of 6,374, followed by University of Nigeria, University of Lagos and Obafemi Awolowo University. CU led the Nat. Sci and Eng & Tech. field with 3,184, 2,630 publications respectively. The University of Nigeria led Soc. Sci. field with 1,733 publications while Ahmadu Bello University led the H&Arts field with just 48 publications. Notably, CU also led the multidisciplinary research with 494 publications.

Table 4.10 Institutional Productivity across OCED Disciplines

Institutions involved	OECD Discipline						
	Agricultural and veterinary sciences	Engineering and technology	Humanities and the arts	Medical and health sciences	Multidisciplinary	Natural sciences	Social sciences
Ahmadu Bello University	750	1107	46	1972	248	825	234
Bayero University	298	713	29	1818	118	590	280
Covenant University	218	2630	44	505	494	3184	584
Federal University of Technology, Akure	761	1261	8	639	179	1065	156
Obafemi Awolowo University	721	1031	21	2527	265	1392	666
University Of Benin	348	449	11	1787	126	535	271
University Of Ibadan	1582	1255	23	6374	436	2003	1277
University Of Ilorin	890	1223	38	1959	243	1306	513
University Of Lagos	359	1299	26	2916	311	1220	640
University Of Nigeria	1153	2181	39	4337	373	2967	1733
Grand Total	7080	13149	285	24,834	2793	15,087	6,354

Figure 4.21 also shows the share of research production per disciplines for each of the top institutions but in a more conspicuous manner, giving insights into which discipline is driving productivity in the specific institutions. Clearly, the M&Hsc field drives the productivity of most Nigerian institutions, however CU distinguishes itself, focusing more on Nat. Sci. and Eng. Tech, research than on M&Hsc.

Figure 4.21: Productivity Distribution of Top Ten Institutions by Discipline

4.3 Discussions of Findings

This study examined research productivity trends in Nigeria between 2014 and 2023, focusing on publication output, collaboration patterns, and disciplinary contributions. The findings revealed significant growth in research output, shifting collaboration dynamics, and variations in productivity across institutions and disciplines. These findings provide insights into Nigeria's research landscape and its positioning in global academic contributions.

Aligning our findings with the existing global and regional trends earlier reviewed in literature, the results show an overall growth in research output from 6,442 publications in 2014 to 19,206 in 2023, with a total of 122,891 publications over the ten-year period. This growth suggests an increasing commitment to research among Nigerian scholars. This aligns with global patterns highlighted in the literature, where countries in developing regions are increasingly contributing to scientific production. Diop and Asongu (2023) observed similar trends in African research, citing that while African countries are still catching up to global output levels, countries like Nigeria have shown significant improvement in research output in recent years

The analysis of Year-over-Year (YoY) growth and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) further confirms an upward trajectory in research output, albeit with fluctuations in specific years. Nigeria's CAGR for this period is well above the world average growth of 3.6% and a strong contender for when compared with the growth rate recorded by some G-20 countries with 199 - 2022s (China 9.3% and India 9.7%, U.S 0.5%) (Carlos, 2023). The plateau observed in recent years may indicate potential challenges such as funding constraints or shifts in institutional priorities. Literature indicates that despite growth, developing countries like

Nigeria continue to face obstacles, including limited funding and brain drain. As highlighted by Egbetokun et al. (2020), these constraints hinder research output and quality, especially as skilled researchers migrate for better opportunities abroad.

Conversely, the impact of collaboration on research productivity is significant. The results suggest that fostering global partnerships could be an effective strategy for boosting research productivity. This aligns with Nigeria's ongoing focus on internationalising its research institutions and building networks with foreign universities. Adelowo et al. (2022) and the OECD studies emphasise the significant benefits of international collaboration, which align with the findings of higher citation rates in international partnerships in this study. This correlation between collaboration and productivity emphasises that building international networks can be a strategy for improving Nigeria's research impact.

The findings on collaboration levels are consistent with studies by Adelowo et al. (2022) and Uwizeye et al. (2021), who indicated that international partnerships yield a higher impact by providing Nigerian researchers with access to better resources and publication opportunities in high-impact journals. This study supports the observation that international collaborations, primarily with the United States and the United Kingdom, substantially increase visibility and citation counts.

On the side of other collaboration types, the limited engagement in local and regional collaborations aligns with Afolabi et al. (2019), who found that Nigerian researchers often prioritise international partnerships for higher impact and funding opportunities. Expanding regional collaboration is an area for improvement, as it could enhance Nigeria's contributions to addressing shared African challenges such as public health and agriculture.

Furthermore, the analysis of author productivity revealed that 92.4% of authors contributed only one publication over the period, while very few researchers produced a substantial number of publications. This finding aligns with Lotka's Law, which predicts that most authors publish only a few papers, while a small percentage are highly productive. The sharp drop in authorship frequency as the number of publications increases indicates a need for greater institutional support to encourage sustained research output.

Similarly, Federal institutions' dominance in research output aligns with previous studies suggesting that government funding and infrastructure are primary drivers of research productivity. The dominance of federal institutions, like the University of Ibadan and University of Nigeria, reflects findings from Salisu and Salami (2020), who argued that government-backed institutions generally outperform others due to greater access to funding and resources. This trend corroborates the literature, showing how federal support significantly contributes to an institution's research productivity.

Federal institutions dominate the top ranks, likely due to more substantial funding and resources. University of Ibadan holds the top spot with 13,122 publications, reflecting robust research output across various fields. The results indicate that federal institutions are likely to benefit from more consistent funding, demonstrate higher productivity than private and state institutions. An additional finding of this study grounded in literature is the positive impact of funding and on research productivity.

Egbetokun (2022) demonstrated that increased funding correlates strongly with higher research productivity. This study's findings, which highlight funding as a key driver of productivity, support this conclusion. Efforts to increase funding allocation, especially for federal institutions, would likely continue to drive productivity.

Federal institutions lead in productivity and recent findings also indicate growth in private universities, such as Covenant University. This aligns with observations by Bonaccorsi et al. (2021), who noted that institutions, regardless of ownership, can achieve high productivity levels if they maintain adequate resources and support systems. Covenant University displays a sharp rise from 2019, indicating its growing role in Nigerian research.

University of Nigeria and University of Ibadan exhibit a balanced distribution across local, regional, and international collaborations, which suggests diversified research networks. Other institutions, by contrast, are more likely to engage in local collaborations, likely due to resource limitations and network constraints. Also, regional collaboration is generally lower across institutions, which may highlight a potential area for growth within Africa.

Notably, groups of interesting findings emerge from the discipline-specific analysis. The study confirms that Medical and Agricultural Sciences dominate research productivity in Nigeria. Okafor (2010) and Salisu and Salami (2020) previously highlighted that fields addressing societal needs, like health and food security, receive more attention and funding. This study reinforces that these fields align with Nigeria's national priorities. Lower output in Social Sciences and Humanities reflects findings by Ani and Bosire Onyancha (2012), who found that these fields often lack adequate funding and collaboration opportunities, especially internationally. This study suggests that targeted investments in these fields could create a more balanced research landscape in Nigeria.

As noted by Bonaccorsi et al. (2021), disciplinary differences are substantial, with fields like Environmental Sciences and Engineering showing rapid growth in response to global priorities. This study corroborates the literature by demonstrating that these fields attract higher collaboration rates and output, reflecting a shift in Nigeria's research focus towards globally relevant topics like climate change and AI

The strengths in fields such as Medical Sciences and Engineering reflect Nigeria's focus on pressing societal issues and technological advancement. This study aligns with Bonaccorsi et al. (2021), who highlighted that nations often focus their research efforts on fields closely tied to development goals. The prominence of health-related research suggests a focus on addressing public health challenges, likely influenced by national and global health priorities. Additionally, agriculture and environmental studies reflect concerns over food security and climate change.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Introduction

This chapter presents a synthesised summary of the core purpose, method and key findings of this study. It then provides a contextual conclusion based on the findings and the empirical evidence from previously reviewed literature which corroborates them. Finally, it features relevant recommendations that can be harnessed to tackle many of the issues deliberated while highlighting areas for further studies which can leverage on the few limitations of the present study to provide more contributions to knowledge.

5.2 Summary of the Findings

The study analysed research productivity and collaboration trends in Nigeria over a ten-year period (2014–2023). It found that research output increased by 11.54%, with 122,891 publications recorded during the period. However, after 2021, the growth rate slowed, indicating the need for strategies to sustain research expansion. Federal universities emerged as the dominant contributors to research output, benefiting from stronger government funding and institutional support.

The disciplinary analysis revealed that Medical and Health Sciences led in research productivity, followed by Natural Sciences and Social Sciences. This trend aligns with global patterns, where applied sciences receive more funding and attention due to their direct impact on societal issues. However, social sciences and humanities have lagged, likely due to inadequate funding and limited international collaboration.

The study also identified a highly skewed authorship pattern, with 92.4% of authors publishing only once during the study period. This suggests that research engagement in Nigeria is not sustained over time, highlighting the need for institutional policies that promote continuous scholarly productivity. Establishing mentorship programs and supporting early-career researchers could help address this issue.

Collaboration trends showed that international partnerships had a positive impact on research output. Nigerian researchers frequently collaborated with scholars from the United States and the United Kingdom, which enhanced research quality. However, regional collaborations within Africa remained underdeveloped, limiting the country's role in intra-African research initiatives.

The study also examined institutional performance and found that federal universities consistently outperformed state and private institutions in terms of research output. This is largely due to government funding and better research infrastructure. However, a few private institutions, such as Covenant University, have shown significant growth in research productivity, signaling a shift in the traditional dominance of federal universities.

5.3 Conclusion

This study highlights the progress and challenges in research productivity and collaboration in Nigeria over the past decade. Research output has increased, with federal universities leading due to better funding and institutional support. However, Nigeria's research productivity is not as poor as depicted in some literatures. Although, despite this progress, growth has slowed since 2021, which indicates the need for policies that ensure sustainable research engagement. A more balanced distribution of research efforts across institutions and disciplines is crucial for sustaining growth.

The findings reveal disciplinary disparities, with Medical and Health Sciences dominating research output, while the social sciences and humanities remain underfunded. This imbalance suggests a need for diversified funding strategies that support underrepresented fields. Encouraging interdisciplinary research and broadening research priorities can enhance Nigeria's contributions to global knowledge production.

The study also exposes a skewed authorship pattern, where most researchers publish only once, reflecting limited long-term engagement in research activities. To address this, institutions should strengthen mentorship programs, provide incentives, and implement policies that encourage sustained research productivity. Academic institutions must also reduce administrative burdens on researchers to create more time for scholarly activities.

Collaboration plays a crucial role in enhancing research productivity, yet Nigeria's regional partnerships within Africa remain weak compared to international collaborations. While partnerships with the U.S. and U.K. have boosted productivity, expanding African collaborations would enable Nigerian researchers to tackle shared challenges and influence regional policies. Strengthening intra-African research networks is essential for long-term impact.

5.4 Recommendations

- **Increase Research Funding and Accountability:** The Nigerian government and funding agencies should allocate more resources to research and development, ensuring that institutions receive adequate support for scholarly work. Additionally, the TETFund should be mandated to provide yearly justification for every fund channeled into research, defined by the number of research publications. Transparent accountability measures should be implemented to prevent mismanagement and foster trust in research investment.
- **Encourage Sustainable Research Engagement:** Policies should be designed to reduce one-time authorship trends by providing incentives for continuous research participation. Offering grants, awards, and funding for high-impact research can encourage sustained productivity. Additionally, researchers should be encouraged to engage in long-term projects and collaborate more frequently to produce multiple publications while increasing cross-disciplinary research efforts to strengthen research impact and address complex societal challenges.

- **Diversify Research Priorities Across Disciplines:** Government agencies and institutions should ensure balanced research funding across various disciplines, including the social sciences and humanities, which are often underfunded. Encouraging interdisciplinary research can enhance knowledge integration and contribute to holistic national development.
- **Enhance Research Collaboration and Networks:** International partnerships have contributed significantly to research growth, however, Nigerian institutions need to actively promote regional collaborations within Africa. Special focus should be given to partnerships with leading research nations in the Sahara region, such as Egypt and Algeria, to improve intra-regional knowledge exchange. Universities should also foster collaborations with global research institutions to enhance funding opportunities and research impact.

5.5 Suggestions for Further Studies

1. **Comparative Analysis of Research Productivity:** A benchmark analysis comparing Nigeria's performance with other African nations—considering factors like GDP ratio to research output—could provide deeper insights into whether Nigeria is reaching its full research potential. Additionally, a comparative study of Nigeria's research productivity relative to other African countries would highlight regional strengths and weaknesses, informing strategies for enhancing Nigeria's competitiveness in both continental and global research landscapes.
2. **Citation Analysis for Research Impact:** Complementing productivity analysis with citation-based metrics, such as citation counts, h-index, and impact factors, could provide a richer understanding of the influence and relevance of Nigerian research beyond publication volume. This approach would ensure that future assessments prioritise both quality and quantity in evaluating research contributions.
3. **Funding Allocation and Research Productivity:** A detailed analysis of funding distribution within Nigerian institutions, including department-specific budgets, research grants, and support structures, could provide clarity on how different funding mechanisms impact research output. Identifying the link between resource allocation and productivity trends would help shape more effective research funding policies.
4. **Barriers to Sustainable Research Engagement:** Given the prevalence of one-time authorship, future research should investigate the institutional and other barriers that prevent Nigerian scholars from sustaining long-term research engagement. Examining the impact of factors such as funding stability, mentorship, and institutional policies could lead to strategies for improving continuous scholarly contributions.

5.6 Limitations of the Study

In this study, the data sources present the major constraints encountered. As mentioned in the chapter three, the Scopus database does not capture all Nigerian research publications, especially those published in local or regional journals not indexed by Scopus. This limits the representativeness of the findings, as a portion of Nigerian research output, particularly, those in underrepresented fields may be overlooked.

From the other sources, the absence of other Nigerian tertiary institutions like polytechnics and colleges of education limits their representation in the study. They were exempted due to the unavailability of consolidated and trusted data which contained their names. Although the impact of this limitation is quite negligible as only about 12.8% of the dataset could not be associated with any research institution, majorly because they were not considered in the list of Nigerian institutions involved in the study.

Also, this study was unable to conduct an in-depth benchmark analysis which could really help contextualise Nigeria's performance globally and within Africa. This is due to the time constraint, considering the duration of the project. However, this was partially remedied by comparing Nigeria's performance to the global research productivity average, which also gave a relative insight into the nation's research growth over the ten-year period amongst other countries.

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APPENDICES

Appendix I: Full list of Collaborating countries with Nigeria

Sn	Country	Publication count
1	United States	11603
2	Egypt	1845
3	Mexico	1138
4	India	5885
5	Japan	1697
6	Malaysia	8734
7	South Africa	13519
8	Thailand	1626
9	Pakistan	2175
10	United Kingdom	10609
11	Cameroon	1154
12	China	5473
13	Sweden	1178
14	Norway	900
15	Serbia	798
16	Spain	1443
17	Saudi Arabia	2974
18	Australia	3017
19	Italy	2193
20	Canada	3102

21	Cote D'Ivoire	370
22	Colombia	735
23	Iraq	805
24	Tunisia	389
25	Iran	1300
26	Portugal	988
27	Germany	3214
28	Belgium	1115
29	Mozambique	357
30	Turkey	1981
31	Palestine	169
32	Burkina Faso	452
33	Senegal	472
34	Uganda	1593
35	Austria	647
36	Finland	660
37	Denmark	624
38	Algeria	360
39	Ghana	2522
40	Congo	388
41	Slovenia	190
42	Nepal	367
43	Switzerland	1521

44	Peru	472
45	Israel	546
46	Netherlands	1667
47	Poland	864
48	France	1851
49	Lebanon	460
50	New Zealand	816
51	Brazil	2009
52	Romania	643
53	Bulgaria	303
54	Russian Federation	992
55	South Korea	1063
56	Cyprus	506
57	Indonesia	1057
58	Singapore	491
59	Madagascar	114
60	Zambia	511
61	Ethiopia	1281
62	Kenya	2175
63	Gambia	431
64	Zimbabwe	417
65	Oman	374
66	Botswana	438

67	Niger	186
68	Tanzania	1012
69	Slovakia	236
70	Philippines	528
71	Greece	628
72	Hong Kong	899
73	Ireland	594
74	Sudan	466
75	Mauritius	134
76	Ukraine	301
77	Cambodia	296
78	Azerbaijan	74
79	Laos	61
80	Ecuador	208
81	Viet Nam	931
82	Bangladesh	785
83	Togo	306
84	Yemen	233
85	Chile	567
86	Venezuela	115
87	United Arab Emirates	900
88	Kuwait	233
89	Argentina	564

90	Sri Lanka	300
91	Uzbekistan	65
92	Benin	526
93	Guinea	155
94	Namibia	286
95	Sierra Leone	274
96	Kazakhstan	244
97	Iceland	97
98	Czech Republic	479
99	Croatia	349
100	Malawi	487
101	Hungary	340
102	Georgia	436
103	Rwanda	513
104	Malta	116
105	Afghanistan	141
106	Luxembourg	126
107	Central African Republic	36
108	Morocco	436
109	Mali	311
110	Gabon	77
111	Angola	51
112	Taiwan	731

113	Lithuania	298
114	Trinidad And Tobago	101
115	Costa Rica	143
116	Bahrain	130
117	Belarus	78
118	Brunei Darussalam	149
119	Paraguay	62
120	Liberia	165
121	Jordan	513
122	Chad	68
123	Burundi	80
124	Myanmar	106
125	Qatar	389
126	Panama	133
127	Estonia	231
128	North Macedonia	81
129	Anguilla	45
130	Jamaica	134
131	Uruguay	169
132	Fiji	112
133	Papua New Guinea	57
134	Syrian Arab Republic	87
135	Mongolia	82

136	Libyan Arab Jamahiriya	43
137	Honduras	39
138	Haiti	41
139	Cuba	66
140	Barbados	65
141	Lesotho	62
142	South Sudan	55
143	Guyana	124
144	Puerto Rico	56
145	Guatemala	79
146	Bolivia	70
147	Libya	161
148	Latvia	101
149	Nicaragua	37
150	Bosnia And Herzegovina	84
151	Somalia	72
152	Democratic Republic Congo	274
153	Albania	101
154	Kyrgyzstan	92
155	Dominican Republic	36
156	Swaziland	118
157	Armenia	59

Appendix II: Full list of Collaborating countries with Nigeria

Sn	Label	Clusters	Links	Documents	Citations	Norm. citations	Avg. pub. year	Avg. citations	Avg. norm. citations
1	wiwanitkit v.	248	0.00	167	179	10.25	2016	1.07	0.06
2	kleebayoon a.; wiwanitkit v.	145	0.00	157	262	98.83	2023	1.67	0.63
3	joob b.; wiwanitkit v.	140	0.00	142	196	11.01	2017	1.38	0.08
4	mungmunpantipanti p r.; wiwanitkit v.	159	0.00	107	108	21.08	2022	1.01	0.20
5	iii	124	0.00	93	895	103.97	2021	9.62	1.12
6	sookaromdee p.; wiwanitkit v.	231	0.00	62	51	8.71	2022	0.82	0.14
7	ozili p.k.	222	0.00	58	888	145.53	2022	15.31	2.51
8	loto r.t.	152	0.00	52	515	30.01	2019	9.90	0.58
9	wiwanitkit s.; wiwanitkit v.	247	0.00	51	55	2.74	2016	1.08	0.05
10	jr.	141	0.00	48	973	61.09	2019	20.27	1.27
11	yasri s.; wiwanitkit v.	250	0.00	48	26	2.21	2018	0.54	0.05
12	oyelude a.a.	219	0.00	37	128	9.93	2019	3.46	0.27
13	idumah c.i.	115	0.00	35	1129	228.72	2022	32.26	6.54
14	emetere m.e.	93	0.00	33	161	9.68	2018	4.88	0.29
15	owolabi k.m.	215	0.00	29	866	54.78	2019	29.86	1.89
16	omoderero c.o.	203	0.00	28	155	13.35	2021	5.54	0.48
17	amah o.e.	53	0.00	26	130	12.38	2022	5.00	0.48
18	kalantar-zadeh k.; li p.k.-t.; tantisattamo e.; kumaraswami l.; liakopoulos v.; lui s.-f.; ulasi i.; andreoli s.; balducci a.; dupuis s.; harris t.; hradsky a.; knight r.; kumar s.; ng m.; poidevin a.; saadi g.; tong a.	142	0.00	26	46	4.82	2021	1.77	0.19

19	mahamood r.m.; akinlabi e.t.	155	0.00	26	599	28.81	2017	23.04	1.11
20	abbasi k.; ali p.; barbour v.; benfield t.; bibbins-domingo k.; erhabor g.e.; hancocks s.; horton r.; laybourn-langton l.; mash r.; sahni p.; sharief w.m.; yonga p.; zielinski c.	1	0.00	25	7	2.65	2023	0.28	0.11
21	nnolim u.a.	165	0.00	25	227	15.00	2019	9.08	0.60
22	li p.k.-t.; garcia- garcia g.; lui s.-f.; andreoli s.; fung w.w.-s.; hradsky a.; kumaraswami l.; liakopoulos v.; rakhimova z.; saadi g.; strani l.; ulasi i.; kalantar-zadeh k.	149	0.00	23	173	12.71	2020	7.52	0.55
23	okonofua f.	189	0.00	23	11	0.91	2020	0.48	0.04
24	shehu y.	227	0.00	23	166	8.57	2015	7.22	0.37
25	chimakonam j.o.	81	0.00	22	371	21.56	2018	16.86	0.98
26	ighravwe d.e.; oke s.a.	120	0.00	22	275	17.25	2018	12.50	0.78
27	ogbuewu i.p.; mbajiorgu c.a.	177	0.00	22	43	11.79	2023	1.95	0.54
28	langham r.g.; kalantar-zadeh k.; bonner a.; balducci a.; hsiao l.-l.; kumaraswami l.a.; laffin p.; liakopoulos v.; saadi g.; tantisattamo e.; ulasi i.; lui s.-f.	146	0.00	20	16	2.48	2022	0.80	0.12
29	nelson e.-u.e.	161	0.00	20	100	11.33	2020	5.00	0.57
30	anyim w.o.	59	0.00	19	31	2.30	2020	1.63	0.12
31	endong f.p.c.	96	0.00	19	13	0.75	2019	0.68	0.04

32	gervasi o.; murgante b.; misra s.	107	0.00	19	0	0.00	2020	0.00	0.00
33	jha b.k.; aina b.	136	0.00	19	224	11.61	2017	11.79	0.61
34	saganuwan s.a.	226	0.00	19	148	8.88	2019	7.79	0.47
35	adeola o.	18	0.00	18	33	2.41	2021	1.83	0.13
36	loto r.t.; loto c.a.	153	0.00	18	140	8.66	2019	7.78	0.48
37	tella a.	235	0.00	18	95	7.02	2018	5.28	0.39
38	okokpujie i.p.; tartibu l.k.	188	0.00	17	16	4.26	2023	0.94	0.25
39	uduji j.i.; okolo- obasi e.n.; asongu s.a.	238	0.00	17	402	36.37	2020	23.65	2.14
40	aborisade r.a.	4	0.00	16	163	20.88	2021	10.19	1.30
41	chukwumah i.	83	0.00	16	11	0.66	2018	0.69	0.04
42	akpomie k.g.; conradie j.	45	0.00	15	405	38.37	2021	27.00	2.56
43	balogun j.a.	75	0.00	15	45	3.86	2021	3.00	0.26
44	igboin b.o.	118	0.00	15	25	3.28	2020	1.67	0.22
45	igwe o.	123	0.00	15	121	5.93	2016	8.07	0.40
46	ike c.c.	125	0.00	15	73	6.19	2020	4.87	0.41
47	inc m.; aliyu a.i.; yusuf a.; baleanu d.	128	0.00	15	463	26.26	2018	30.87	1.75
48	mensah e.o.	156	0.00	15	134	14.38	2021	8.93	0.96
49	adegbite o.	8	0.00	14	1	0.10	2021	0.07	0.01
50	adetayo a.j.	19	0.00	14	98	26.84	2022	7.00	1.92
51	idachaba f.e.	114	0.00	14	32	1.67	2016	2.29	0.12
52	jha b.k.; oni m.o.	138	0.00	14	130	7.83	2018	9.29	0.56
53	oluwole o.s.a.	201	0.00	14	63	3.08	2017	4.50	0.22
54	sriwijitalai w.; wiwanitkit v.	232	0.00	14	20	1.41	2020	1.43	0.10
55	aigbodion v.s.	35	0.00	13	75	7.72	2021	5.77	0.59
56	ajide f.m.	38	0.00	13	177	17.87	2022	13.62	1.37
57	akinbo b.j.; olajuwon b.i.	41	0.00	13	72	7.51	2021	5.54	0.58
58	akinyemi y.c.	43	0.00	13	48	4.58	2020	3.69	0.35
59	amungo e.	54	0.00	13	5	0.36	2020	0.38	0.03
60	big-alabo a.	78	0.00	13	83	5.93	2020	6.38	0.46

61	jha b.k.; samaila g.	139	0.00	13	97	14.64	2022	7.46	1.13
62	olajire a.a.	193	0.00	13	1709	104.12	2018	131.46	8.01
63	uduji j.i.; okolo-obasi e.n.	237	0.00	13	364	26.87	2020	28.00	2.07
64	yusuff a.s.	252	0.00	13	219	19.09	2020	16.85	1.47
65	aladejare s.a.	47	0.00	12	137	23.21	2022	11.42	1.93
66	arowosegbe j.o.	63	0.00	12	84	5.26	2018	7.00	0.44
67	egbueri j.c.	90	0.00	12	681	67.27	2021	56.75	5.61
68	essien e.d.	99	0.00	12	25	1.39	2019	2.08	0.12
69	fabiya o.a.	101	0.00	12	98	11.32	2022	8.17	0.94
70	ighalo j.o.; adeniya a.g.	119	0.00	12	473	35.39	2020	39.42	2.95
71	jha b.k.; malgwi p.b.	137	0.00	12	50	4.39	2021	4.17	0.37
72	lucero-prisno d.e.	154	0.00	12	172	16.30	2022	14.33	1.36
73	odeyemi k.o.; owolawi p.a.; olakanmi o.o.	175	0.00	12	91	8.55	2021	7.58	0.71
74	okeke d.	185	0.00	12	3	0.14	2016	0.25	0.01
75	olukoju a.	199	0.00	12	25	1.75	2020	2.08	0.15
76	uyor u.o.; popoola a.p.i.; popoola o.m.; aigbodion v.s.	242	0.00	12	148	14.59	2020	12.33	1.22
77	ajibade o.a.; agunsoye j.o.; oke s.a.	37	0.00	11	21	1.54	2018	1.91	0.14
78	awonusika r.o.	68	0.00	11	37	3.36	2020	3.36	0.31
79	bamidele o.	76	0.00	11	17	0.80	2016	1.55	0.07
80	daungsupawong h.; wiwanitkit v.	85	0.00	11	8	3.02	2023	0.73	0.28
81	ikeagwuani c.c.; nwonu d.c.	126	0.00	11	302	25.24	2021	27.45	2.30
82	kamil i.a.; ogundoyin s.o.	143	0.00	11	230	18.49	2020	20.91	1.68
83	nnamuchi o.	164	0.00	11	21	1.17	2018	1.91	0.11
84	ozoegwu c.g.	223	0.00	11	229	14.96	2017	20.82	1.36
85	solanke b.l.	230	0.00	11	152	8.62	2018	13.82	0.78
86	adeniya a.g.; ighalo j.o.	15	0.00	10	275	20.94	2020	27.50	2.09

87	adeniyi e.	16	0.00	10	17	2.25	2021	1.70	0.22
88	adibe j.	26	0.00	10	12	0.82	2018	1.20	0.08
89	adigun m.	27	0.00	10	11	0.85	2020	1.10	0.09
90	afolayan a.	29	0.00	10	18	1.00	2019	1.80	0.10
91	awang m.; mohammadpour e.; muhammad i.d.	67	0.00	10	1	0.05	2016	0.10	0.00
92	bingi k.; ibrahim r.; karsiti m.n.; hassan s.m.; harindran v.r.	79	0.00	10	67	4.70	2020	6.70	0.47
93	chiluwa i.	80	0.00	10	109	6.78	2019	10.90	0.68
94	egya s.e.	91	0.00	10	31	2.03	2019	3.10	0.20
95	emetere m.e.; akinyemi m.l.	95	0.00	10	61	2.91	2017	6.10	0.29
96	esoimeme e.e.	98	0.00	10	34	2.28	2019	3.40	0.23
97	imafidon e.	127	0.00	10	35	1.79	2016	3.50	0.18
98	michael m.	157	0.00	10	12	0.68	2018	1.20	0.07
99	njoku e.t.	162	0.00	10	55	5.04	2019	5.50	0.50
100	numbere a.o.	166	0.00	10	50	4.15	2021	5.00	0.42
101	olakanmi o.o.; odeyemi k.o.	194	0.00	10	47	6.95	2022	4.70	0.70
102	olaoluwa s.	195	0.00	10	15	0.90	2019	1.50	0.09
103	olawuyi d.s.	196	0.00	10	91	5.10	2018	9.10	0.51
104	omeje k.	202	0.00	10	3	0.20	2017	0.30	0.02
105	omotoshob j.	205	0.00	10	18	3.95	2019	1.80	0.40
106	omotoso s.a.	206	0.00	10	16	0.92	2019	1.60	0.09
107	popoola l.t.	224	0.00	10	384	29.73	2020	38.40	2.97
108	yahya h.	249	0.00	10	25	1.62	2020	2.50	0.16
109	abdullahi a.	2	0.00	9	93	6.56	2019	10.33	0.73
110	abolarinwa a.	3	0.00	9	50	3.61	2020	5.56	0.40

11 1	adamu a.u.	5	0.00	9	10	0.60	2019	1.11	0.07
11 2	adebayo k.o.	7	0.00	9	24	3.74	2022	2.67	0.42
11 3	adegoke k.; frontczak r.; goy t.	10	0.00	9	12	2.53	2022	1.33	0.28
11 4	adegun o.b.	11	0.00	9	91	9.57	2020	10.11	1.06
11 5	ademiluka s.o.	12	0.00	9	36	2.43	2021	4.00	0.27
11 6	adeniji s.e.; uba s.; uzairu a.	13	0.00	9	65	4.68	2019	7.22	0.52
11 7	adewuyi a.	20	0.00	9	272	26.30	2021	30.22	2.92
11 8	adeyemi w.j.; olayaki l.a.	23	0.00	9	163	9.03	2018	18.11	1.00
11 9	ahmed m.; huq m.s.; ibrahim b.s.k.k.	34	0.00	9	5	0.33	2018	0.56	0.04
12 0	aikhuele d.o.	36	0.00	9	46	3.24	2020	5.11	0.36
12 1	akingboye a.s.; bery a.a.	42	0.00	9	42	7.68	2022	4.67	0.85
12 2	akuru u.b.; kamper m.j.	46	0.00	9	120	6.27	2018	13.33	0.70
12 3	aniche e.t.	56	0.00	9	57	4.14	2019	6.33	0.46
12 4	anoruo c.m.	57	0.00	9	35	4.14	2021	3.89	0.46
12 5	apuke o.d.; omar b.	60	0.00	9	582	59.65	2021	64.67	6.63
12 6	asongu s.a.; uduji j.i.; okolo-obasi e.n.	64	0.00	9	179	13.16	2020	19.89	1.46
12 7	ayodele j.o.	71	0.00	9	21	1.04	2017	2.33	0.12
12 8	dalamu t.o.	84	0.00	9	17	1.11	2020	1.89	0.12
12 9	evans o.	100	0.00	9	192	12.94	2019	21.33	1.44
13 0	ifejika s.i.	116	0.00	9	3	0.36	2022	0.33	0.04

131	isah a.d.	132	0.00	9	0	0.00	2016	0.00	0.00
132	misra s.	158	0.00	9	62	6.36	2018	6.89	0.71
133	nwagwu w.e.	167	0.00	9	33	2.36	2020	3.67	0.26
134	nwokolo s.c.; singh r.; khan s.; kumar a.; luthra s.	172	0.00	9	2	0.76	2023	0.22	0.08
135	ofuasia e.	176	0.00	9	17	1.94	2021	1.89	0.22
136	ogundoyin s.o.; kamil i.a.	178	0.00	9	188	22.65	2021	20.89	2.52
137	ogunmiloro o.m.	179	0.00	9	33	4.13	2022	3.67	0.46
138	okechi n.f.; asghar s.	184	0.00	9	59	4.63	2020	6.56	0.51
139	okeniyi j.o.; loto c.a.; popoola a.p.i.	187	0.00	9	250	15.03	2015	27.78	1.67
140	onaolapo a.y.; onaolapo o.j.	208	0.00	9	119	8.00	2020	13.22	0.89
141	onaolapo o.j.; onaolapo a.y.	209	0.00	9	53	3.80	2020	5.89	0.42
142	oyewole s.	220	0.00	9	127	6.23	2017	14.11	0.69
143	tade o.	234	0.00	9	23	1.79	2020	2.56	0.20
144	umukoro n.	239	0.00	9	33	2.24	2018	3.67	0.25
145	unuabonah f.o.	240	0.00	9	60	4.70	2019	6.67	0.52
146	uroko f.c.	241	0.00	9	3	0.41	2022	0.33	0.05
147	adegoke k.	9	0.00	8	19	1.29	2018	2.38	0.16
148	adeniyi a.a.; conradie j.	14	0.00	8	50	3.73	2019	6.25	0.47
149	adeniyi m.o.	17	0.00	8	77	4.66	2017	9.63	0.58
150	adewuyi a.; oderinde r.a.	21	0.00	8	73	9.71	2020	9.13	1.21

151	adeyeye s.a.o.	25	0.00	8	225	10.62	2017	28.13	1.33
152	afisi o.t.	28	0.00	8	8	0.71	2021	1.00	0.09
153	agbo c.o.a.	31	0.00	8	4	0.32	2021	0.50	0.04
154	agunloye o.m.; oboh g.	33	0.00	8	110	9.69	2020	13.75	1.21
155	akinbinu v.a.	40	0.00	8	72	3.39	2017	9.00	0.42
156	alao m.a.; popoola o.m.; ayodele t.r.	48	0.00	8	133	17.98	2022	16.63	2.25
157	amaefule a.e.	52	0.00	8	15	2.03	2022	1.88	0.25
158	anetor l.; osakue e.e.; odetunde c.	55	0.00	8	19	1.22	2019	2.38	0.15
159	aregbeshola b.s.; khan s.m.	61	0.00	8	287	16.66	2018	35.88	2.08
160	attoe a.d.	65	0.00	8	43	4.98	2020	5.38	0.62
161	ayenigbara i.o.	69	0.00	8	17	2.33	2022	2.13	0.29
162	ayoade m.a.	70	0.00	8	35	1.97	2020	4.38	0.25
163	ayodele t.r.; ogunjuyigbe a.s.o.	72	0.00	8	321	15.18	2016	40.13	1.90
164	babatunde a.o.	74	0.00	8	47	3.28	2019	5.88	0.41
165	bamidele s.	77	0.00	8	10	0.66	2019	1.25	0.08
166	diala i.	86	0.00	8	23	1.21	2019	2.88	0.15
167	ejegwa p.a.	92	0.00	8	353	27.80	2021	44.13	3.47
168	emetere m.e.; akinlabi e.t.	94	0.00	8	0	0.00	2020	0.00	0.00
169	fasan r.	103	0.00	8	26	1.26	2018	3.25	0.16
170	fayemi a.k.	104	0.00	8	24	1.43	2018	3.00	0.18

171	gervasi o.; murgante b.; misra s.; gavriloa m.l.; rocha a.m.a.c.; torre c.; taniar d.; apduhan b.o.	108	0.00	8	4	0.19	2016	0.50	0.02
172	ibanga d.-a.	110	0.00	8	24	1.48	2020	3.00	0.19
173	ifezue d.; tobins f.h.	117	0.00	8	13	0.73	2015	1.63	0.09
174	ighravwe d.e.; oke s.a.; adebiyi k.a.	121	0.00	8	39	1.93	2017	4.88	0.24
175	inyinbor a.a.; adekola f.a.; olatunji g.a.	130	0.00	8	727	35.12	2017	90.88	4.39
176	iwuoha v.c.	134	0.00	8	50	3.49	2020	6.25	0.44
177	lawal s.l.; afolalu s.a.; jen t.-c.; akinlabi e.t.	148	0.00	8	3	1.13	2023	0.38	0.14
178	loto c.a.	150	0.00	8	386	18.65	2017	48.25	2.33
179	nathaniel s.p.	160	0.00	8	351	34.50	2021	43.88	4.31
180	nkeki c.i.	163	0.00	8	36	2.09	2017	4.50	0.26
181	obayelu a.e.	173	0.00	8	21	1.20	2017	2.63	0.15
182	odeyemi k.o.; owolawi p.a.	174	0.00	8	30	2.78	2020	3.75	0.35
183	ogunyemi k.	180	0.00	8	9	0.57	2017	1.13	0.07
184	okeke i.n.	186	0.00	8	37	2.05	2019	4.63	0.26
185	okorie n.	190	0.00	8	12	1.02	2022	1.50	0.13
186	olujobi o.j.	198	0.00	8	158	13.43	2020	19.75	1.68
187	omoderi c.o.; alege p.o.	204	0.00	8	9	1.46	2022	1.13	0.18

188	onanuga p.a.	207	0.00	8	43	4.37	2021	5.38	0.55
189	onwubiko e.c.	210	0.00	8	4	0.30	2020	0.50	0.04
190	tursunbadalov s.; soliev l.	236	0.00	8	90	4.57	2017	11.25	0.57
191	welcome m.o.	245	0.00	8	193	13.38	2020	24.13	1.67
192	yusuf h.o.	251	0.00	8	6	0.56	2020	0.75	0.07
193	adebayo i.g.; sun y.	6	0.00	7	32	2.45	2020	4.57	0.35
194	adeyanju o.a.; oyekunle l.o.	22	0.00	7	53	3.60	2017	7.57	0.51
195	adeyeri j.o.	24	0.00	7	2	0.12	2019	0.29	0.02
196	agada a.	30	0.00	7	38	4.11	2021	5.43	0.59
197	agu h.u.; gore m.l.	32	0.00	7	37	3.06	2022	5.29	0.44
198	ajimotokan h.a.	39	0.00	7	8	0.38	2022	1.14	0.05
199	akpan b.	44	0.00	7	1	0.05	2020	0.14	0.01
200	aliu i.r.	49	0.00	7	37	3.42	2020	5.29	0.49
201	aliyu a.i.; inc m.; yusuf a.; baleanu d.	50	0.00	7	150	8.93	2018	21.43	1.28
202	amadasun s.	51	0.00	7	169	14.19	2021	24.14	2.03
203	anyanechi c.e.; saheeb b.d.	58	0.00	7	35	2.34	2016	5.00	0.33
204	armstrong i.	62	0.00	7	6	0.72	2022	0.86	0.10
205	atwoli l.; erhabor g.e.; gbakima a.a.; haileamlak a.; ntumba j.-m.k.; kigera j.; laybourn-langton l.; mash b.; muhia j.; mulaudzi	66	0.00	7	5	1.00	2022	0.71	0.14

	f.m.; ofori-adjei d.; okonofua f.; rashidian a.; el- adawy m.; sidibé s.; snouber a.; tumwine j.; yassien m.s.; yonga p.; zakhama l.; zielinski c.								
20 6	babarinde t.o.; akinlabi s.a.; madyira d.m.	73	0.00	7	79	6.26	2020	11.29	0.89
20 7	choji n.m.; sek s.k.	82	0.00	7	6	0.31	2019	0.86	0.04
20 8	dumbili e.w.	87	0.00	7	69	5.40	2019	9.86	0.77
20 9	ebekozien a.	88	0.00	7	148	13.65	2021	21.14	1.95
21 0	edomah n.	89	0.00	7	95	7.49	2020	13.57	1.07
21 1	enyimba m.	97	0.00	7	16	1.41	2022	2.29	0.20
21 2	faleye o.a.	102	0.00	7	33	4.32	2019	4.71	0.62
21 3	filani i.	105	0.00	7	46	2.89	2019	6.57	0.41
21 4	fowowe b.	106	0.00	7	367	18.68	2017	52.43	2.67
21 5	hassan s.m.; ibrahim r.; saad n.; bingi k.; asirvadam v.s.	109	0.00	7	19	1.35	2020	2.71	0.19
21 6	ibhagui o.	111	0.00	7	14	1.29	2020	2.00	0.18
21 7	ibrahim m.t.; uzairu a.; shallangwa g.a.; uba s.	112	0.00	7	80	5.92	2020	11.43	0.85
21 8	ibrahim r.l.; ajide k.b.	113	0.00	7	358	40.53	2021	51.14	5.79
21 9	igibah e.c.; agashua l.o.; sadiq a.a.	122	0.00	7	8	0.58	2019	1.14	0.08

220	inc m.; yusuf a.; aliyu a.i.; baleanu d.	129	0.00	7	278	15.20	2018	39.71	2.17
221	iorliam a.	131	0.00	7	5	0.28	2018	0.71	0.04
222	iwegbue c.m.a.	133	0.00	7	105	5.45	2015	15.00	0.78
223	jacob j.u.-u.	135	0.00	7	15	0.89	2017	2.14	0.13
224	kleebayoon a.; mungmunpantipanti p r.; wiwanitkit v.	144	0.00	7	1	0.38	2023	0.14	0.05
225	lawal k.a.	147	0.00	7	41	2.62	2017	5.86	0.37
226	loto c.a.; loto r.t.	151	0.00	7	32	2.00	2018	4.57	0.29
227	nwankwo c.f.	168	0.00	7	31	2.58	2020	4.43	0.37
228	nwankwo w.; ukhurebor k.e.	169	0.00	7	87	7.09	2020	12.43	1.01
229	nwanzu c.l.; babalola s.s.	170	0.00	7	52	4.35	2020	7.43	0.62
230	nwedu c.n.	171	0.00	7	18	1.45	2020	2.57	0.21
231	ohimain e.i.	181	0.00	7	153	7.37	2016	21.86	1.05
232	ojaruega e.e.	182	0.00	7	14	0.84	2019	2.00	0.12
233	okafor k.c.; longe o.m.	183	0.00	7	23	3.40	2022	3.29	0.49
234	okoro r.n.	191	0.00	7	31	2.93	2021	4.43	0.42
235	okuonghae r.i.; ikhile m.n.o.	192	0.00	7	16	1.00	2015	2.29	0.14
236	ololube n.p.	197	0.00	7	5	0.30	2016	0.71	0.04
237	oluwajobi a.o.; chen x.	200	0.00	7	6	0.30	2016	0.86	0.04
238	onwude d.i.; hashim n.; abdan k.; janus r.; chen g.	211	0.00	7	373	24.08	2018	53.29	3.44

23 9	onyelowe k.c.	212	0.00	7	124	8.20	2018	17.71	1.17
24 0	osaghae e.e.	213	0.00	7	19	0.90	2018	2.71	0.13
24 1	oshewolo s.	214	0.00	7	47	3.54	2019	6.71	0.51
24 2	owolabi k.m.; pindza e.	216	0.00	7	74	9.04	2022	10.57	1.29
24 3	oyebode o.j.	217	0.00	7	11	1.93	2022	1.57	0.28
24 4	oyelade a.o.	218	0.00	7	72	5.25	2019	10.29	0.75
24 5	oyeyinka o.	221	0.00	7	10	0.47	2017	1.43	0.07
24 6	sadiq m.s.; singh i.p.; ahmad m.m.	225	0.00	7	3	0.28	2021	0.43	0.04
24 7	shehu y.; iyiola o.s.	228	0.00	7	201	9.77	2018	28.71	1.40
24 8	singh j.; taura j.j.	229	0.00	7	41	2.75	2014	5.86	0.39
24 9	strang k.d.; vajjhala n.r.	233	0.00	7	29	2.74	2021	4.14	0.39
25 0	vajjhala n.r.; strang k.d.	243	0.00	7	16	1.46	2020	2.29	0.21
25 1	wapmuk s.	244	0.00	7	2	0.21	2019	0.29	0.03
25 2	williams d.u.	246	0.00	7	2	0.31	2019	0.29	0.04

**Appendix III: Yearly Authorship Distribution of Nigeria's Research Publications from
2014 - 2023**

Figure III.1 Authorship Distribution for 2014

Figure III.2 Authorship Distribution for 2015

Figure III.3: Authorship Distribution for 2016

Figure III.4: Authorship Distribution for 2017

Figure III.5: Authorship Distribution for 2018

Figure III.6: Authorship Distribution for 2019

Figure III.7: Authorship Distribution for 2020

Figure III.8: Authorship Distribution for 2021

Figure III.9: Authorship Distribution for 2022

Figure III.10: Authorship Distribution for 2023